

COMBATING INFLATION: THE CASE OF AMBULANT VENDORS IN THE CITY OF KORONADAL

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ABSTRACT

This study delved into the experiences on combating inflation of the three ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal. The study utilized a multiple – holistic qualitative case study which allowed to closely look at the participants' experience of inflation, and of combating it and the interventions provided by the government to them. The researchers conducted a one-on-one interview aided by an interview guide and observation checklist to gather the data and information needed for the study. The results indicated that the ambulant vendors faced price fluctuations in both the commodities they purchased and the products they sold, prompting changes in purchasing behavior. Despite the challenges, the vendors exhibited resilience by adopting proactive strategies to mitigate the effects of inflation. However, they also raised a concern on the absence of financial assistance of the government which may help them lessen the impacts of inflation. To address this concern, the researchers recommended a clearer and more concise governmental support to help them combat inflation.

Keywords: *Ambulant vendors, experiences, combating inflation, intervention of the government*

INTRODUCTION

An economy's average price level consistently rising is referred to as inflation (Andres & Hernando, n.d). It occurs when the average price level increases over time which Kirshner (2011) argued that political conflicts, are the cause of inflation at all rates, high and low. For instance, the Russian invasion of Ukraine is cited to continue to affect the world's supply chains thus worsening the inflation. Due to war's shortages and escalating food prices, there is now more food and services insecurity which greatly affect vendors especially those who own a small business like street or ambulant vendors (Nyagudi, 2022).

Inflation can impact the global economy both individuals and businesses. It diminishes the purchasing power of money so people must spend more money to acquire the same quantity of products and services. This can result in a decline in living standards for many individuals (Fernando, 2023). According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), world inflation reached 8.8% in 2022. The prognosis is adversely impacted by the rising cost of living, tightening financial conditions across the board, Russia's invasion of Ukraine, and the persisting COVID-19 pandemic. Forecasts predict that the rate of global inflation would increase from 4.7% in 2021 to 8.8% in 2022 before falling to 6.5% in 2023. In the Philippines, the Philippine Statistics Authority (2023) data show that the Philippine inflation rate marginally slowed down to 8.6% in February 2023, from 8.7% in January 2023, and it continued to decline to 7.6% on March 2023. In South Cotabato, the inflation rate, increased from 7.3% in January 2023 to 7.6% in February 2023, but it slowed down to 7.3%. As stated by Homes (2022) in the Philippines, inflation raised production costs, including raw material, labor, and other inputs, reducing vendors profitability and slowing economic activity.

Inflation is believed to affect the ambulant vendors (Ordinario, 2021). Ambulant vendors are individuals who sell goods or services on the streets, often in urban areas. In countries experiencing high inflation, these vendors may face challenges related to pricing, demand, and supply (Buzzell, 2014). Furthermore, Chen, & Simchi-Levi (2012) claimed that the escalation in prices of goods and commodities is attributed to the Law of Supply and Demand underscores the importance of aligning consumer preferences with product demand. This highlights that the supply-demand imbalance in the dual-channel supply chain can have a significant impact on optimal pricing and inventory strategies. Inflation results in the loss of sales to larger competitors who offer lower prices or better deals, ambulant vendors who need significant sales volumes to stay profitable may find this difficult (Weber, 2020). That is why some ambulant vendors choose to buy in wholesale to save money and some buy in retail everyday to avoid spending much and there are some who depends on their salary that is based on their quota. Inflation can cause prices to rise rapidly and unpredictably, making it difficult for ambulant vendors to set prices that are both affordable for their customers and profitable for themselves. They may struggle to keep up with changing prices and may find that their profit margins are shrinking as the cost of goods and services increase

(Recchi, 2021). Furthermore, inflation may increase demand for certain goods and services, as consumers seek out cheaper alternatives to more expensive products.

According to Zhu and Simarmata (2015), in some cases, inflation may also lead to shortages of certain goods, which can make it difficult for ambulant vendors to find the products they need to sell. This can lead to reduced sales and income and may force vendors to diversify their offerings or switch to selling alternative products. As the data presented by the DTI the City of Koronadal in the year 2022 has the biggest revenue in South Cotabato in their economic activity that have the total amount of Php 1,204, 850, 160.49. According to Hayes (2023) revenue is the money earned through routine business operations. It means that a higher revenue a higher economic activity which means that a lot of vending activities is happening.

In the City of Koronadal, the City Treasurer office states that in the year 2023 there are approximately 236 ambulant vendors who contributed to daily vending activities of the city and at the same time they are experiencing and continuing to combat the political phenomenon of inflation. In addition, the LGU of City of Koronadal estimates that there were 236 regular ambulant vendors, 34 salary-based ambulant vendors, and 15 occasional ambulant vendors in the month of April.

This study identified a group of ambulant vendors in Koronadal City as the researchers found out that they were one of the significant groups that directly deal with inflation and have a hard time combating the effects of the phenomenon. The researchers intend to describe the phenomenon of combating inflation by the ambulant vendors using a case study approach and through the lens of Modern Liberalism.

Research Questions

Generally, the study aimed to describe the phenomenon combating inflation as experienced by the ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How do the ambulant vendors experience inflation?
2. How do the ambulant vendors combat inflation?
3. What are the interventions provided by the government to the ambulant vendors?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The design of the research study is a Multiple - Holistic case study. It focused on the ambulant vendors of the Koronadal City on their mechanism to combat inflation. The identified participants are the regular ambulant vendors, occasional ambulant vendors, and salary – based ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal. The regular ambulant

vendors go about their everyday business of selling their product. They purchased everyday raw materials and necessary ingredients in their livelihood to maintain their vending business. Occasional ambulant vendors would operate by intervals depending on whether their space is filled by another seller or not, and it would only engage in selling activities if there were an event that was taking place, such as a festival or Valentine's Day. The Salary-based Ambulant vendors are those who are paid a salary and whose business equipment is owned by someone else and who are compensated based on a percentage of their daily sales quota. Multiple Holistic approach will be utilized to describe the experience of the ambulant vendors in combating inflation. It allowed the researchers to compare the commonalities and differences in multiple perspectives and it will give a better approach in the formulation of the data given by the participants considering that they form in a same unit of analysis but draw a different context in every aspect of vending activities to combat the existing phenomena.

The researchers conducted face-to-face in-depth interview which is the most suitable and conducive instrument for collecting the necessary data. A face-to-face interview is a form of data collecting in which the interviewer talks directly with the participant in line with the prepared questionnaire. This method allows for the collection of factual information, participants assessments, attitudes, preferences, and other information gleaned from the respondent's dialogue. In-depth interviews were conducted by the researchers in order for them to have detailed information about on combating inflation regarding on their experiences, and challenges and coping mechanism. In the analysis of the data, the researcher used thematic analysis to create themes that describe their experience to combat inflation and cross-case analysis that allows the comparison of the commonalities and differences and to have a general overview on the experiences of the ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal.

Setting

This study was conducted in the City of Koronadal, South Cotabato. It is located in Southern Mindanao, in the province of South Cotabato and a third-class component city in the Philippines. It is the seat of the provincial capitol of South Cotabato and one of the province's only two cities. Koronadal is currently a rapidly growing growth economic hub comprised of twenty-seven (27) barangays, including the poblacion's four (4) zones. Being the capital city of South Cotabato, it serves as the province's political, cultural, and socioeconomic hub.

The researchers chose this particular setting because it is the capital of the province and it is around where most of the vending and other economic activities are done by the locals. In particular, there are approximately 286 ambulant vendors residing in City of Koronadal who experienced the political phenomenon of inflation. Moreover, based on the records by the LGU of City of Koronadal, there is an estimate of 236 regular ambulant vendors, 34 salary-based ambulant vendors and 15 occasional ambulant vendors for the month of April.

Participants

The researchers identified the prospective participants of this study based on the inclusion criteria set by the researchers. First, the participants must be an ambulant vendor living in the City of Koronadal. Second, the participants must at least have 5 years of vending here in City of Koronadal and have selling any kind of goods or offering repair services. Third they are willing to participate in the study and have agreed to be interviewed.

The participants of this study were three (3) vendors in the City of Koronadal. They spent numerous years in vending in a different location around in the City of Koronadal and trying to survive their livelihood as a vendor despite the effects of the inflation. They have different contextual conditions. Participant 1 is a Regular Ambulant Vendor who does his vending activities daily; participant 2 is an Occasional Ambulant Vendor who does her vending activities during major events; participant 3 is a Salary – Based Ambulant Vendor who does her vending activities with a consistent salary.

Participant 1: Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV)

The first participant is a 32-year-old fruit vendor, a resident of Barangay GPS in Koronadal City. He has been in the business for eight (8) years, starting in 2015. This dedicated family man lives under one roof with his wife, three (3) children, and his parents. His business took an unexpected turn when the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the usual flow of life. Before the pandemic, he used to sell his selection of fresh, seasonal fruits in the Koronadal City Public Market. However, due to the strict safety protocols and concerns posed by the pandemic, he had to adapt and relocate his stall. He now operates near the highway of Marbel 1 Elementary School on Morales Avenue, conveniently close to his home.

Participant 2: Occasional Ambulant Vendor (OAV)

The second participant is a 38-year-old ukay-ukay seller who has been in the business for more than five years. She operates three stalls around the city, though they are temporary and are primarily set up during significant occasions such as the T'nalak Festival or the Charter Anniversary. Her day typically begins at around 7 in the morning when she sets up her stall, and she keeps it open until the end of the event or late at night when the number of visitors dwindles. She does not limit her operations to the physical stalls; she has also expanded into online selling. Her primary business involves offering secondhand clothing items at affordable prices.

Participant 3: Salary-based Vendor (SAV)

The third participant is a 23-year-old salary-based vendor from Koronadal, South Cotabato. For the past five years, he has been working in an *aripahol* business. This food business has been around for nine years and has multiple branches in different locations within the city. The vendor's stall is strategically located beside the City Health Office, right next to a street crossing. He works for his cousin, whom he met under unfortunate circumstances – during an accident. This led him to *aripahol* vending, where he now helps his parents earn money for his school expenses. His workday begins at 7 in the morning

and concludes at 7 in the evening. Rain or shine, he diligently works to sell food products to passersby. His dedication is further rewarded by the fact that the business owner provides him with all the necessary ingredients and equipment. Additionally, his unique work arrangement grants him incentives such as free boarding, food, water, and electricity, as his boss happens to be a relative.

Instruments

In this study, the researchers used two (2) instruments namely: observation checklist and interview guide. Observation checklist is a record of events, conversations, and behaviors observed in the field, as well as the researcher's reflections on them. Then, the researchers formulated an original interview guide based on our specific research problems. The research interview guide is the most basic interview guide but contains the primary data of the study and the interview data as well. The instrument is subject to extensive examination and thorough deliberation through constant consultation with the thesis adviser. After the consultation, the instrument used by the researchers in their one-on-one and face-to-face interview with the participants of the study. A set of questions were put together with the purpose to obtain necessary data and information to describe the experiences in combating inflation of the vendors in City of Koronadal. It consists of the three major questions that will help the researchers to gather and generate data. The first question of the interview guide pertains to how the ambulant vendors experience inflation; the second question asks about how the ambulant vendors combat inflation; and the third question asks about the intervention provided by the government to the ambulant vendors.

Data Gathering Procedure

First, the researchers conducted a direct observation in the community in order to identify the current situation of the ambulant vendors and their experience in combating inflation. Second, the researchers conducted an interview dry run and generated an initial analysis to have a preliminary data about their experience on combating inflation and before the official interview, the researchers asked permission from the Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences of Notre Dame of Marbel University. After the researchers acquired the required signatories and consent, the researchers went to the place where vendors do their vending business.

The researchers then introduced themselves to each participant during a subsequent visit. Next, the researchers adhered to the necessary ethical standards during the conduct of the study and presented the consent letter to the participants following the interview. Then, with the help of the interview guide, the researchers conducted one-on-one and in-depth interviews with the three vendors selected as the study's cases in order to collect the necessary data until the study was complete.

Throughout the duration of the discussion, the three ambulant vendors described their experiences with inflation, on how they combat inflation, and the intervention provided by the government to them. All data and information were gathered and collected using an audio-recorded file, which were carefully analyzed. The recordings were deleted after the finalization of the study.

Data Analysis

The interview data were transcribed verbatim. Identified the significant statement, then directly address the interview questions that had been drawn and analyzed individually to draw out their meaning. Formulated meanings for each of the significant statements were crafted and concepts were assigned. The concept in turn were clustered and their common themes were drawn to answer the specific research problems.

After analyzing each of the case, cases 1 and 2 werer cross-analyzed. Similarities and differences between the themes of each case was drawn out the analysis. Findings were cross-case analyzed with the case 3 to drawn out the similarities and differences of the themes.

The study used a thematic analysis based on Braun and Clarke and cross-case analysis drawn from the paradigm of Yin as the primary means of data analysis in this study. Thematic analysis was used to understand the patterns of meanings from the data on the experiences of the vendors in the City of Koronadal. After the researchers used thematic analysis, cross-case analysis was also used to thoroughly understand and describe the comparison and commonalities based on the themes and meanings from the experiences of the vendors as they battle to combat the inflation.

Limitation of the Study

The subject of this study is limited only to the ambulant vendors residing in the City of Koronadal. The respondents were selected through the inclusion criteria, and through the face-to-face in-depth interview, the researchers gathered and recorded all necessary data. The researchers limited the number of participants to a regular ambulant vendor, an occasional ambulant vendor and a salary-based ambulant vendor; they are the only main source of data.

The limitation also includes the availability of data and information regarding the profile of ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal taken from the city government. Another condition that limits the study is the option of ambulant vendors to refuse to participate due to their busyness engaging in their business or other personal reasons. Other unavoidable limitations of the study include time limit, budget, and the openness of the identified ambulant vendors.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the study on how the ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal experience inflation, combat inflation and the interventions provided by the government. The succeeding sections are organized based on the identified cases of the study.

CASE 1: RAV (Regular Ambulant Vendor)

The first participant is a 32-year-old fruit Regular Ambulant Vendor, a resident of Barangay GPS in Koronadal City and at the same time an alumnus of Notre Dame of Marbel University. He has been in the business for eight (8) years, starting in 2015. This

dedicated family man lives under one roof with his wife, three children, and his parents. His business took an unexpected turn when the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted the usual flow of life. Before the pandemic, he used to sell his selection of fresh, seasonal fruits in the Koronadal City Public Market. However, due to the strict safety protocols and concerns posed by the pandemic, he had to adapt and relocate his stall. He now operates near the highway of Marbel 1 Central Elementary School at Morales Avenue, conveniently close to his home. Now he is currently selling variety of fruits with the help of his nephew. He wakes up at 4 a.m. to ready the fruits for selling, commencing his vending activities by 7 a.m. and continuing until 7 p.m. His merchandise includes avocados, lanzones, rambutan, and durian. Furthermore, He always sells his products daily in the same location. He owns the business and establishes his locations in an exact same place every day. With this, they are one of the participants of the interview that was conducted last August 15, 2023, at 2:00 in the afternoon. He shared and answered the questions attentively and willingly. He was incredibly attentive and enthusiastic to share his experience on inflation, on how he combats inflation and the intervention of the government provided to address inflation.

The next sections show the themes from the significant statements of vendor about their experiences during inflation.

Experience of Inflation by Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV)

This section provides the themes of ambulant vendors in their experience during inflation period, their most difficult experience during inflation period, their perceived reason of the increased prices and commodities and their perceived effects of increased price and commodities.

Vending Experience of RAV During Inflation

During Inflation, price fluctuating is experienced by the regular ambulant vendor (RAV) due to the availability (or unavailability) of product as well as the gasoline price fluctuation.

In table 1 RAV talked about his experiences during inflation in which the themes are increased supply of in season fruits making the price lower than usual and increased price of gasoline which make the price of fruits higher than usual. RAV stated that *“Gaabot tanan kilo sang tig 15-20 ang kilo sang rambutan kag lansones pag season, pero subong daw dira na lang sya sa 30-40 per kilo, nag epekto gd.”* This was explained by Silver (2016) that during an inflationary period, the doubling of fruit prices can be attributed to a confluence of factors, primarily rooted in the demand-pull theory of inflation. The demand-pull theory of inflation posits that changes in the level of aggregate demand within an economy are the primary drivers of inflationary pressures.

Furthermore, RAV also shared insights into his experiences during inflation with the theme increased price of gasoline which make the price of fruits higher than usual. RAV stated the price of gasoline necessarily results in increase of prices. He said that *“Dati ang mangga mahal kai 150 to 180 kag kis a pa kalab ot mana 200/kg na, tung mahal pa na ang gasoline”.*

Table 1. Vending Experience of RAV During Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
tao gareklamo kai sa kamahal kailangan man kami magpataas kai gagamit kami gasoline	People were complaining because of expensive price of fruits cost of transportation of fruit production and distribution, which involve gasoline usage, has increased, leading to the adjusting the price of the fruits to accommodate these rising costs	Dissatisfaction of customers in terms of pricing Increasing the price of the fruits
Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Gaabot tanan kilo sang tig 15,20 ang kilo sang rambutan kag lansones pag season, pero subong daw dira na lang sya sa 30, 40 per kilo, nag epekto gd. Pero daw subong nga 2023 daw nagbaba na ang 874asoline, medyo nagbarato man ang baraklon. Dati ang 874asol mahal kai 150 to 180 kag kis a pa 874asoline mana 200/kg na, tung mahal pa na ang 874asoline.	During Lansones and Rambotan season, price per kilo is cheap. Now, the price has doubled As price of gasoline drops, the price of commodities also drops.	Price fluctuation due to - availability or unavailability of products and - gasoline price fluctuation

Most Difficult Experience of RAV During Inflation

During Inflation, RAV most difficult experiences are dissatisfaction of customers in terms of pricing and increasing the price of the fruits.

Table 2. Most Difficult Experience of RAV During Inflation

Table 2 shows the themes of the RAV’s most difficult experiences during inflation. During the interview, he shared that, there are customers who complained about the high prices of fruits. *“Ang tao gareklamo kai sa kamahal”* he said. As prices rise, consumers find that the same amount of money can buy fewer goods and services. This experience according to Edward (2000) can lead to dissatisfaction and frustration among the population, especially those on fixed incomes. Moreover, RAV added that with the high cost of transportation he is left with no choice but to increase the price of the fruits he sells albeit grudgingly. He stated *“kailangan man kami magpataas kai gagamit kami gasoline”*. This was confirmed in the study by Forage (2023,) he said that as the gasoline continue to rise and inflation continue to exist, vendors should also adjust their prices to maintain their profit and income in their business. Inflation leads to an increase in the cost

of production. Businesses may face higher expenses for raw materials, labor, utilities, and other operational costs.

Perceived Reason for the Increased Prices of Commodities of RAV

In the surge of inflation, the RAV perceived factors affecting the price increase, the table 3 below shows the RAV perceived reasons of the increase prices and commodities which are the External Factors and Procedural Factors.

RAV perceived reasons for the increase prices and commodities on what he experiences and notices during the inflation period. This was supported by the findings of Zhao (2021) that ambulant vendors, like many individuals in various sectors, may have perceptions about the reasons for inflation. As for the RAV, he emphasized that the *“number 1 [factor] is ...gasoline”*. Referring to the procedural dimension of production, he stated that, *“...maagi pa na sa harvester kag sa financer kag patungan pa nila na, itrucking pa”* Weather, for him is also a factor as he said that *“.ning tig ulan. Pero may time gd abi nga may weather nga di magbunga ang prutas*. This claim was confirmed by Wichmann, Uppal, Sharma, & Dekimpe, (2022) in their study, they explained that understanding the interplay between these external and procedural factors is essential for businesses, and consumers to navigate the complexities of price determination in an economy.

Table 3. Perceived Reason for the Increased Prices of Commodities of RAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Themes
number 1 gani gasolina. tapos maagi pa na sa harvester kag sa financer kag patungan pa nila na, itrucking pa Kis a siguro, ning tig ulan. Pero may time gd abi nga may weather nga di magbunga ang prutas	The gasoline is the primary cause of the high prices of goods Another factor of causing high prices is the cost of the procedure from harvester, financer and supplier Another factor of the high prices is on the season or weather	Factors affecting the prices, such as: External: gas price, weather condition Procedural: shipping, production

Perceived Effects of Increased Prices of Commodities to RAV

The table 4 below shows the themes of the RAV perceived effects of the increased prices of commodities. He answered a feeling of disappointment and income or profit loss due to: Few products being sold and spoilage.

Inflation, as a pervasive political phenomenon, affects the ambulant vendors in various ways. RAV shared that because of inflation few were being sold which resulted in the spoilage of a large number of fruits, he said *“mabulukan ka pa dako man ang maloss sa imo, amo na sya isa pa na”*. He emphasized that there is a great loss to his income whenever fruits were spoiled, according to him *“mabulukan ka pa dako man ang maloss sa imo, amo na sya isa pa na”*. The effect of the inflation to the RAV was explained by Garg (2022) he said in his study that the effects of this phenomenon can jeopardize the

financial stability of the business. It may impact the ability to invest in improvements or expansion

Table 4. Perceived Effects of Increased Prices of Commodities to RAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
<p>syempre ma dismay ko mabulukan ka pa dako man ang maloss sa imo, amo na sya isa pa na.</p> <p>Pag hindi mabakal pagkabwas madunot na sya. Wala na, malugi ka na sina</p>	<p>Disappointed</p> <p>When price of fruits is high, few customers buy fruits resulting further in spoilage and eventually, income or profit</p> <p>Loss of profit due to unsold fruits</p>	<p>Income/ Profit loss due to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Few products being sold due to high price 2. Spoilage

Regular Ambulant Vendor on Combating Inflation

This section provides the identified themes of regular ambulant vendor in combating inflation. This includes the strategies and ways of the ambulant vendors on how they combat inflation. Lastly, it includes the challenges and difficulties faced by the ambulant vendors it is combating inflation.

Strategy of RAV to Combat Inflation

The table 5 shows the identified themes of the regular ambulant vendor use strategies of RAV to combat inflation which includes the adaptation strategies to mitigate the impacts of inflation.

Table 5. Strategy of RAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
<p>katu kai free delivery mo amo to ang offer ko sa ila. pasuki suki gihapon. Ang mga suki ko ara gihapon. Nagbalhin lang ko sa elementary banda katong pandemic kag tong pagtaas sang presyo, Nagbaylin kami didtu sa highway banda kai ginaagyan ka lang sang mga tao sa gawas na lang ko parehas sa highway banda.</p>	<p>Offering a free delivery service to the consumers</p> <p>Acquiring a loyal and regular customer to ensure profit</p> <p>Change location near the highway where mostly people pass</p>	<p>Adaptation strategies to mitigate the impacts of inflation</p>

RAV combat inflation with the theme adaptation strategies to mitigate the impacts of inflation. RAV utilizes various strategies to alleviate the effects of inflation such as, offering a delivery service, acquiring a loyal customer and changing the location. First strategy he utilized is he changed location to attract more customers, he stated that “*Nagbaylin kami didtu sa highway banda kai ginaagyan ka lang sang mga tao,*” he also emphasized the importance of having a loyal customer as a strategy to ensure profit, he stated that “*pasuki suki gihapon. Ang mga suki ko ara gihapon.*”. Lastly, he pointed out the need for flexibility as he was offering a free delivery service to his consumers he said “*katu kai free delivery mo amo to ang offer ko sa ila.*”. These utilizing strategies was explained by Mecalux (2017) as he stated that adapting several strategies can mitigate the impact of inflation and implementing innovative marketing strategies allows businesses to navigate rising expenses associated with inflation, helping to maintain or improve profit margins. on the cost of goods and services.

Ways of RAV to Combat Inflation

The table 6 shows the identified themes of the regular ambulant vendor his way and style to combat inflation which is the RAV became thrifty to save money.

Table 6. Ways of RAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Gacontrol lang gd sang baraklon eh Tapos waay na gd kaayo kami galagaw sa mall Siguro kis a ga tyanggi tyanggi na lng gd kami. Di na mabakal sang isa ka gallon nga mga tuyo, or vinegar tyanggi tyanggi na lang sachet na lang anay.	Limiting the purchasing behavior to avoid spending much Restricting ourselves to purchase in the malls Choosing to purchase in a neighborhood sundry store to avoid spending much Choosing to purchase retail rather wholesale	RAV became thrifty to save money

Thrifty individuals are more intentional and selective about their purchases. They carefully consider whether an expense is necessary and if there are more cost-effective alternatives. RAV emphasizes that one of his ways to combat inflation and lessen its impact is to become thrifty in his buying behavior. He stated that “*Gacontrol lang gd sang baraklon*” This was affirmed by Ailawadi, K. L., Neslin, S. A., & Gedenk, K. (2020) that thrifty individuals are adept at strategic shopping. They seek out sales, discounts, and utilize coupons to secure the best deals and one way to mitigate inflation. Moreover, they

opt for generic or store brands, recognizing that quality need not always come with a hefty price tag.

Challenges and Difficulties of RAV to Combat Inflation

The table shows the themes of the challenges and difficulties of regular ambulant vendor to combat inflation which is reduced buying behavior.

Table 7 Challenges and Difficulties of RAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
<p>budlay mag dispose gd Di ko maka kompra sang damo kai mahal Nabudlayan ka mag dispose sang baligya kai dati makadisperose ko sang sobra hundred kilos per day pero sang inflation na dira na lang sa 30 kilos Ti naggamay ang sales ko kai ang nagnubu ang akong produkto</p>	<p>Difficulty in selling fruits to customers Cannot purchase wholesale products because of high cost Difficulty in selling fruits to customers and decreasing the sales during high inflation rate Sales were decrease because of limited products</p>	<p>Reduced buying behavior</p>

Table 7 shows the reduced buying power poses a significant challenge in combating inflation. In the study of Hayes (2015), if the buying behavior of the individual diminishes, individuals and businesses face several difficulties that can affect their financial well-being. This was shown on the experiences of the RAV when he said that his sales were decreased because of the products unsold due to the reduced buying behavior of the consumer. He stated that “*Ti naggamay ang sales ko kai ang nagnubu ang akong produkto*”. In addition, he himself also had a hard time as a consumer and not a vendor because before, he can buy things for his business a larger scale but due to inflation it reduces. He said that: *Di ko maka kompra sang damo kai mahal*. In that same article of Haynes (2015), he confirmed that a significant change in buying behavior can lead to a decline in the standard of living. Individuals may find it challenging to afford the same level of goods and services they enjoyed before, affecting their overall quality of life.

Government Interventions provided to the Regular Ambulant Vendor

This section provides the identified themes of regular ambulant vendor in the government intervention provided by the state. This includes the assistance and any forms of help from the government.

Interventions of the Government to RAV

Table 8 shows the themes of the interventions of the government to mitigate the impacts of inflation which the themes identified that RAV did not receive any kind of financial assistance from the government.

Table 8 shows the lacking financial assistance of the government. The programs offered by the government seems to be impossible to fulfill by an ordinary citizen. In the study of Igudia (2019), he states that since ambulant vendors often do not pay formal taxes, the government might not feel obligated to provide them with financial assistance. This is in reality as was experienced by the regular ambulant vendor, stating that ... *Gahatag man lang abi na sila sa ila nga programa kung daw makita nila nga may pigado..* In his statement, he confirms that sometimes the government does not felt obligated to provide financial assistance to him. Also, RAV directly said that he did not feel any assistance from the government but upon the observation of the researchers with the help of observation checklist, they observed that there are constant police officers roaming around in his area. This is aligned in the ideals of Thomas Green in his Modern Liberalism. According to the theory of Modern Liberalism, it states that the government will focus on the security and give the people the freedom in their own business.

Table 8. Interventions of the Government to RAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meaning	Themes
wala pasila kahatag sang bulig. Kay syempre di ko qualified abi. wala gihapon. Gahatag man lang abi na sila sa ila nga programa kung daw makita nila nga may pigado nga ano. daw di ko man abi maramdaman ang kwan sang gobryerno ba di namon mabal an nga ila nga mga programa. Waay man ko to nag apply tung TUPAD para sa trabaho no. wla man ko kaapil sato.	None. Vendors Did not receive any help due to qualification requirement None. Government only aid when it became obvious that poverty is beyond the line. None. vendor cannot Feel the Assistance of Government Vendor don't know the existing programs Vendor did not apply to TUPAD, (an assistance provided for the ambulant vendors)	The Vendor did not receive any kind of financial assistance from the government

Schematic Diagram of RAV Themes

The schematic diagram serves as a comprehensive synthesis of the prevailing themes derived from the analysis of significant statements. It encapsulates a wealth of information that directly addresses the core research problem. Within the diagram, themes are artfully represented through a symbiotic interplay of symbols, arrows, and lines. These graphical elements not only identify the relationships between various components but also offer a visual narrative that elucidates the intricate

interconnectedness of the identified themes. Upon distinguishing the themes that experienced by RAV during the inflation, it was evidently recognized that increased price of gasoline, high demand on supplies and products, and limited supply chain are leading causes of inflation. It is enclosed within one setting to highlight the key components to why products increased in prices. The two-sided arrow with dashed lines indicates interrelatedness of factors such weather condition and of seasonal products as well as the transportation challenges to sudden price increased of products of the vendor, that could lead to potential loss of income due to customers dissatisfaction and probably spoilage of products. The curly braces are used to correlate the variables of existing factors of vendor during inflation to separate it from how the adaptation of strategies to combat inflation are utilized. It was seen that thrifty behavior and reduced purchasing power of vendor shows interrelatedness, and the result of the vendor's strategy. Government aid and programs are separate variables to distinguish how was the vendors are capable of living with or without the intervention of the government, thus curly braces are also used. However, it was shown that vendor is not knowledgeable about it.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the themes of RAV

CASE 2: OAV (Occasional Ambulant Vendor)

OAV is a 38-year-old ukay-ukay seller who has been in the business for more than five years. She is an Occasional Ambulant Vendor who does not sell daily, only for some special Filipino events to sell her goods or merchandise. She sets up her business only during major events. She does not have a permanent location to do her vending business,

only on during the locations provided by different LGUs during an event. In this case, she sells her products on the Charter Anniversary of the City of Koronadal. She operates three stalls around the city, though they are temporary and are primarily set up during significant occasions such as the T'nalak Festival or the Charter Anniversary.

Currently her ukay-ukay business is in front of Rizal Park in City of Koronadal while it celebrates its charter anniversary. Her life and livelihood here typically begin at around 7 in the morning when she sets up her stall, and she keeps it open until the end of the event or late at night when the number of visitors dwindles. She does not limit her operations to the physical stalls; she has also expanded into online selling. Her primary business involves offering secondhand clothing items at affordable prices. The life of this ukay-ukay seller is one of adaptability and seizing opportunities, often aligned with the city's major events and celebrations.

The next sections show the themes from the answer of the occasional ambulant vendor about her experiences during inflation.

Experience of Inflation by Occasional Ambulant Vendor (OAV)

This section provides the themes of occasional ambulant vendors in their experience during inflation period, their most difficult experience during inflation period, their perceived reason of the increased prices and commodities and their perceived effects of increased price and commodities.

Vending Experience of OAV During Inflation

The table 9 shows the themes of the occasional ambulant vendor experiences during inflation period which she experienced Financial Constraints.

Table 9. Vending Experience of OAV During Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
kis-a kulang pa ang benta namon sa amon needs adlaw-adlaw ...Di kaayo kusog ang sales.	money earned from vending sales is insufficient to cover the daily expenses financial earnings are relatively small	Financial constraints

OAV as an ambulant vendor who does her vending business on some major events such as festivals or anniversaries is also affected by inflation. She shows her dissatisfaction as she experienced moving in her business in a tight budget and having financial constraints. She stated that. " *kis-a kulang pa ang benta namon sa amon needs adlaw-adlaw*". Then she also shared how her earnings got increased, she expressed that "...*Di kaayo kusog ang sales*". This turn of events is affirmed by Hardie (2023), he said that with inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder. Occasional vendors frequently juggle other commitments like

childcare or primary jobs, making extended hours or adjusting prices less feasible. This can further squeeze their earnings.

Most Difficult Experience of OAV During Inflation

The table 10 shows the themes of the occasional ambulant vendor’s most difficult experience during inflation period which are increased prices of product and reduced number of customers.

Table 10. Most Difficult Experience of OAV during Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
ang gina bakal namon, naga taas man gyapon. Kay syempre ang dati ang bundle is mura-mura lang, subong mahal na gid. grabe pag bawas ka customers namon, may ara man japon pero lain gd tung dati	The cost of a bundle of shirts has increased compared to the previous period when they were more affordable Unexpected decrease of customers due to expensive cost of goods	Increased price of products Reduced number of customers

As inflation continue to affect the prices of the products clothes and apparel business is also affected. A study conducted by Gu, Ślusarczyk, Hajizada, Kovalyova, & Sakhbieva, (2021), when they claim inflation have affected many businesses, including the apparel industry. The cost of raw materials, production, and transportation has increased, leading to higher prices for goods. This has resulted in an unexpected decrease in customers for many businesses as consumers become more price conscious. This was visible in the answer of OAV as her most difficult experience during inflation period. She shared that the cost of the bundle shirts which she sells became expensive, she said “*ang gina bakal namon, naga taas man gyapon. Kay syempre ang dati ang bundle is mura-mura lang, subong mahal na gid*” and her disappointment became worse when she said that due to the expensiveness of her products she experiences the reduction of her customers, she shared “*grabe pag bawas ka customers namon , may ara man japon pero lain gd tung dati*”.

Perceived Reason for the Increased Prices of Commodities of OAV

The table 11 shows the themes of the occasional ambulant vendor’s perceived reason for the increase prices of commodities which are the shipment process, and fuel and transportation impact on pricing.

Table 11. Perceived Reason for the Increased Prices of Commodities of OAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
<p>“Damo... kumbaga, ang mga supplier gahatag pa na sa customs. Kumbaga damo pa sang SOP, damo pa sang gina tagaan. Kaagi gani kami, ang bundle namon ging confiscate sang customs sa port...”</p> <p>“kung gataas gd ang gasoilina mag umpisa gd na tarag.as ka mga presyo”</p>	<p>The high cost of goods can be largely attributed to the expenses incurred in the product shipping process.</p> <p>If there is an increase in gasoline prices, it will lead to a corresponding rise in the prices of other products</p>	<p>Shipment process affects in the increase prices</p> <p>Fuel and transportation impact on pricing</p>

Shipment process, fuel cost and transportation expenses are identified by the OAV as perceived reasons why the prices of commodities continue to rise. She said shipment process from the Bureau of Custom until the products reach her, that largely contribute to the increase of prices, she said *“Damo... kumbaga, ang mga supplier gahatag pa na sa customs. Kumbaga damo pa sang SOP, damo pa sang gina tagaan. Kaagi gani kami, ang bundle namon ging confiscate sang customs sa port...”*. Then, she did equate in her perceived reason the prices of fuel and gasoline as one of the major factors contributing to the increasing prices of commodities she explained *“If there is an increase in gasoline prices, it will lead to a corresponding rise in the prices of other products”*.

Perceived Effects of Increased Prices of Commodities to OAV

The table shows the themes of the occasional ambulant vendor’s perceived effects of the increased prices of commodities which is changed buying behavior resulted in changed consumer behavior.

Table 12. Perceived Effects of Increased Prices of Commodities to OAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
<p>“kung kis-a dati gabakal-bakal pa ta sang isa ka sako nga bugas diba? Tapos subong, kung kis-a kilo-kilo ka nalang kay tungod sa kataason”</p> <p>dati maka grocery kita within 1 month or 1 week, subong hindi na kay tungod sang kataason sang mga baraklon</p>	<p>The OAV used to be able to purchase an entire sack of rice in the past, but presently, they can only afford to buy a few kilograms of rice due to a change in their financial situation or economic circumstances</p> <p>The ability of the OAV to afford an adequate supply of groceries, emphasizing the decrease of quality the OAV purchased</p>	<p>Reduced purchasing behavior and a changed consumer behavior</p>

Table 12 shows OAV perceived effects of prices of commodities. OAV commented about how her capacity to buy basic commodities and as rice has been reduced to its ricing price. If in the past, she could afford to buy a sack now “*Kilo-kilo na lang*” according to her. She further noted that there are certain things she could no longer do today as her buying behavior changed., she stated “*dati maka grocery kita within 1 month or 1 week, subong hindi na kay tungod sang kataason sang mga baraklon.*”. This is confirmed in the study of Addeh, Olusola, Chimezie, & Shuuya (2022), where they concluded that the reduced purchasing behavior and changed consumer behavior due to inflation and it can lead to decreased demand for goods and services, which can put pressures on prices. Moreover, it can also lead to decreased economic activity and reduced consumer spending, which can have negative consequences for businesses and the overall economy.

Occasional Ambulant Vendor on Combating Inflation

This section provides the identified themes of occasional ambulant vendors in combating inflation. This includes the strategies and ways of the ambulant vendors on how they combat inflation. Lastly, it includes the challenges and difficulties faced by the OAV in combating inflation.

Strategy of OAV to Combat Inflation

This section provides the identified themes on the strategy of OAV on how she combats inflation which is using online platform as an alternative.

Table 13. Strategy of OAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
Nag resort na lang ko sa online selling, kay para maka dagdag man sang akon ginansya	Resorted to online selling to increase profit.	Using online platform as an alternative

OAV described how she navigated the effects of inflation where she used online platform as an alternative to sustain her vending business. As her number of customers continued to decrease, she resorted to another method to promote her products, that is why she entered the realm of online business. She stated: “*Nag resort na lang ko sa online selling, kay para maka dagdag man sang akon ginansya...*” This was confirmed in the study Luong (2023), street vendors adopt a strategy, utilizing alternative methods to comply with regulations while preserving the tradition of street trading. Despite facing marginalization due to digitalization, these vendors employ effective tactics, seizing opportunities and creating employment despite their limited skills. Their adaptability and resourcefulness demonstrate their capacity to prosper in the midst of urbanization and modernization regardless of economic crisis.

Ways of OAV to Combat Inflation.

This section provides the identified themes on the strategy of OAV on how she combats inflation which is self-reliance and cost efficiency.

Table 14. Ways of OAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
nang instead makuha ka sang tao... Ikaw nalang gid. Instead nga makwa ka sang tao nga mag bantay diba...ang expenses mo ibayad mo sa tao	personal involvement due to the concern that employing staff might lead to higher operational costs.	Self-reliance and cost Efficiency

OAV dealt with the increase in commodity prices in a way of getting directly involved in her business. As she worried about the possible rise in costs, she involves herself into the daily tasks of the business herself. This choice showed a practical response to economic challenges, proving she is focused on making as much money as possible while keeping costs in check. She stated "*Nang instead makuha ka sang tao... Ikaw nalang gid. Instead nga makwa ka sang tao nga mag bantay diba...ang expenses mo ibayad mo sa tao...*" This was proven in the study of Nurjannah and Andiny (2020), they stated that street vendors use workforce of 1-5 people with a wage of Rp. 10,000-Rp. 50,000 or 178-356 Php per day. This compensation structure reflects the informal nature of street vending and the economic constraints faced by this sector. The modest wages are often associated with the informal economy's characteristics, where financial resources are limited, and workers are compensated based on the day-to-day earnings of the business.

Challenges and Difficulties of OAV to Combat Inflation

Table 15. Challenges and Difficulties of OAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
<p>“...kailangan mo mag less expenses ka kay tungod sa income mo hindi sapat...”</p> <p>sa physical store mo kailangan mo pa assistant, sa online selling abi ikaw lang. Pero need mo man gyapon may assistant ka kay syempre mag packing, delivery mo pa.</p> <p>description mo abi kung ihambal mo pa kung ok or good, or kung hindi sila satisfied ibalik pa sa imo. Rekalmuhan ka pa</p>	<p>Vendor had to cut with inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder.</p> <p>Occasional vendors frequently juggle other commitments like childcare or primary jobs, making extended hours or adjusting prices less feasible. This can further squeeze their</p> <p>With inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder.</p> <p>The vendor challenges in online product sales related to the need for detailed descriptions, customer persuasion, and dealing with negative feedback and returns.</p>	<p>Financial struggles and cost Management</p> <p>Lack of human resources and assistance</p> <p>Handling customer complaints</p>

Table 15 shows the themes of the OAV in the challenges and difficulties she encountered when she combats inflation. The identified themes are financial struggles and cost management, lack of human resources and handling customer complaints. With inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder. Occasional ambulant vendors frequently juggle other commitments like childcare or primary jobs, making extended hours or adjusting prices less feasible. This can further squeeze their earnings. With inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder. Occasional vendors frequently juggle other commitments like childcare or primary jobs, making extended hours or adjusting prices less feasible. This can further squeeze their earnings. With inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder. Occasional vendors frequently juggle other commitments like childcare or primary jobs, making extended hours or adjusting prices less feasible. This can further squeeze their earnings.

As the prices continue to rise, OAV do anything she can to combat and fight it in order for her to sustain her livelihood. However, in her ways and strategies in combating

inflation, she faced a lot of difficulties and challenges. She shared that in order for her to fit her profit and her day-to-day expenses she need to lessen her expenses, she said “...*kailangan mo mag less expenses ka kay tungod sa income mo hindi sapat...*”. Also, another challenges she faced is her lack of resources or staff to to help her manage the online and physical selling, she expressed “*sa physical store mo kailangan mo pa assistant, sa online selling abi ikaw lang. Pero need mo man gyapon may assistant ka kay syempre mag packing pa...*”. She faced a lot of challenges and difficulties when she combats inflation, and this phenomenon was explained by Jaishankar and Sujatha (2016). According to them, street vendors, including ambulant vendors, face many challenges as they are a vulnerable population who are not protected by government, with inflation making basic needs more expensive, the choice to vend occasionally becomes even harder. Occasional vendors frequently juggle other commitments like childcare or primary jobs, making extended hours or adjusting prices less feasible. This can further squeeze their earnings. The study also found that street vendors suffer from competition with other vendors due to fluctuation in market prices, insecure and irregular employment, and lack of protection from civic agencies and the state government. These challenges can make it difficult for OAVs to cut down expenses and hire additional staff for packaging and delivery.

Government Interventions provided to Occasional Ambulant Vendor

This section provides the identified themes of occasional ambulant vendor in the government intervention provided by the state. This includes the assistance and any forms of help from the government.

Interventions of the Government to OAV

Table 16 shows the themes of the Government interventions provided to OAV.

Table 16 Interventions of the Government to OAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Theme/s
“ <i>daw wala man, Tung pag pandemic oo, pero wala naman kami sato source</i> ”	The ambulant vendor did not receive any government financial assistance for her clothing business, except during the COVID-19 pandemic, which was unrelated to her business	No financial support

OAV faces the dual challenge of limited financial support and a conscious choice to abstain from pursuing government aid. When asked if she received financial aid from the government when the prices of commodities have begun to increase, OAV replied: “*wala man. Tung pag pandemic oo, pero wala naman kami sato source*”. Opting to maintain regular payments for the occupational tax permit, she showcases a commitment to self-reliance despite the absence of external financial assistance. She added: “*kami pa...gabayad sa government... kay syempre ang permit....*”. She was also cautious in

asking for government aid as it is selectively granted based on specific criteria, she stated: “...ginapili lang man abi kung sin-o lang to ang pwede tagaan. Depende sa imo... kung ano kadako sang business mo...” Although there is no financial assistance in the government, the researchers observed during their interview that there is the presence of police car patrolling the area, thus ensuring peace and security. This claim was supported by the Modern Liberalism theory which advocate minimal intervention and focusing on liberalistic will. In this case, a security assistance was provided by the LGU Koronadal but an absence of financial assistance in combating inflation.

Schematic Diagram of Occasional Ambulant Vendor

The themes in the context of Occasional Ambulant Vendor (OAV) during inflation were summarized and illustrated in a schematic diagram. The primary factor triggering the effects of inflation on the OAV's business is the surge in commodity prices, stemming from increased fuel and transportation expenses. This rise in costs directly affects the prices of goods sold by the OAV, making them less affordable for consumers and has led to a decrease in the number of customers for the OAV. This reduction is attributed to the change in the purchasing power of the consumers. As prices escalate, consumers' ability to afford goods diminishes, resulting in reduced demand for the OAV's clothing products. To counteract the effects of decreased purchasing power and dwindling customers, the OAV opted to utilize online platforms as an alternative sales channel. However, this transition was not without challenges. While exploring online platforms, the OAV found herself in a predicament. In a bid to be cost-efficient, she had to be self-reliant, managing the business operations single-handedly despite the need for additional support. The absence of financial aid or adequate resources made it necessary for her to minimize costs by personally handling sales and operations. Operating both physical and online shops presented challenges for the OAV. Engaging customers in the online sphere required a significant amount of patience and effort. Balancing the demands of both physical and online selling was exhausting and demanding, leading to increased stress and operational challenges. Despite facing multiple challenges and seeking sustainability, the OAV did not receive any financial aid from the government. This lack of support was primarily due to the government's criteria for aid, which favored selectivity and omitted individuals like the OAV, who were self-reliant. The absence of financial aid or adequate resources made it necessary for her to minimize costs by personally handling sales and operations like the OAV.

Figure 2 Schematic Diagram of the Themes of OAV

Cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV in their experience of inflation

This section shows the cross-case analysis of Regular Ambulant Vendor and Occasional Ambulant Vendor in their experience of inflation

Cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV themes in their experience during inflation

The table 17 shows the cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV. It shows the commonalties and differences of the RAV and OAV in vendor experiences during inflation.

Table 17 Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV in Vending experiences during inflation

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
Price fluctuation due to - availability or unavailability of products And - gasoline price fluctuation	Financial Constraints	Both RAV and OAV experienced high cost and unstable prices of products and commodities brought by inflation	OAV nature of business does not constantly relied on the availability of products and they are experiencing financial constraints while the products of the business of RAV relies also on the availability and unavailability of the supply

Table 17 shows the commonalities and distinctions in the themes arising from the responses of RAV and OAV are notable. Both groups, Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV) and Occasional Ambulant Vendors (OAV), share a common theme in dealing with the experiences brought about by the inflation which is driven increase in product costs. The escalating prices of goods and services, coupled with the volatility in pricing, are adversely affecting their means of earning a living. RAV sells variety of fruits. The high cost of these items is directly impacting their profit margins. OAV, who typically sell clothes during a major event such as charter anniversary, is also feeling the pinch of inflation. Prices in her commodities and products increased and experience fluctuation. Those experienced was explained by Thompson (2014) that according to him ambulant vendors often operate on small margins, making it difficult to absorb these cost increases without passing them on to consumers. Furthermore, it was confirmed in another study conducted by Atnafu & Balda (2018) that street vendors may have less flexibility in adjusting their prices, making it even more challenging to maintain profitability. In some cases, they may even be forced to reduce their inventory or stop selling certain items altogether because of continuing rise of prices.

On the other hand, the table 17 shows the differences of the themes between RAV and OAV. The pricing of products sold by Occasional Ambulant Vendor (OAV) is generally less influenced by supply and gasoline prices compared to the products sold by Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV). OAV sells clothes that is not needed to be delivered due to unfixed location or operating on a predetermined schedule. This allows them to have more control over their pricing strategy, as they are not as heavily affected by fluctuations in supply and gasoline costs (Hayes, 2022). RAV, on the other hand, often source their products from various suppliers and may need to adjust their prices frequently based on availability and transportation costs. This makes them more susceptible to the effects of

supply chain disruptions and fuel price increases as explained by Chopra (2014) in his study.

In conclusion OAV has more flexibility in setting her prices and is less affected by external factors such as supply chain disruptions and fuel price fluctuations. RAVs, on the other hand, need to be more dynamic in their pricing strategy to account for changes in supply and transportation costs.

Cross-Case Analysis of themes of RAV and OAV in their most difficult experience during inflation

The table 18 shows the cross-case analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV in their most difficult experience during inflation. It shows the commonalties and differences of the RAV and OAV in vendor experiences during inflation.

Table 18 Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV in their most difficult experience during inflation

RAV	OAV	Commonalties	Differences
Dealing with the dissatisfaction of Customers in terms of pricing Increasing the Price of the fruits	Changed the purchasing behavior of consumers and negatively affect the business by leading to a reduction in the number of customers	Both RAV and OAV most difficult experience during inflation are dissatisfaction and reducing number of customers	RAV experience of having to increase the price despite the dissatisfaction in the price while the OAV changed his attitude in terms of purchasing behavior

The Table 18 shows the commonalties and differences of RAV and OAV in their most difficult experience during inflation. They shared a common theme which are the dissatisfaction of customers of prices and reducing number of customers. These same experiences affirmed in the study of Kenton (2023) that inflation leads to increased costs for goods and services, putting pressure on RAVs and OAVs' profit margins. He added, to maintain profitability, they may have to raise prices, which can further alienate customers who are already struggling with inflation's impact on their purchasing behavior.

Furthermore, the table 18 also shows the differences of the themes of RAV and OAV in their most difficult experience. Regularly increasing the price of fruits due to inflation poses a significant challenge for RAV. This is because according to Mankiw and Reis (2016), customers are more price-sensitive during periods of inflation and raising prices can lead to customer dissatisfaction and a decline in sales. RAV face the dilemma of maintaining profit margins while keeping their products affordable for customers. On the other hand, OAV is more likely to adapt their purchasing habits in response to inflation. This could involve switching to cheaper suppliers, buying smaller quantities of clothes, or choosing a more suitable time for occasions that are less affected by price fluctuations, as explained by Dhar (2022).

Cross- Case Analysis of the themes in Perceived Reasons of RAV AND OAV for the Increased Prices and Commodities

The table 19 shows the cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV. It shows the commonalties and differences of the RAV and OAV in their perceived reasons for the increased prices and commodities.

Table 19 Cross- Case Analysis of the themes in Perceived Reasons of RAV and OAV for the Increased Prices and Commodities

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
Factors affecting the prices, such as: - External: gas price, weather condition Procedural: shipping, production	Fuel and Transportation Impact on pricing	Both RAV and OAV shared that the cost of fuel and shipping process is perceived as a reason why prices of commodities increase	OAV does not equate weather condition as factor why prices increased

Table 19 illustrates the similarities and distinctions between RAV and OAV in terms of how they perceived why prices and commodities increased. RAV and OAV are particularly affected by these rising costs, as they often operate on tight margins and have limited resources to absorb the increased expenses. As a result, Nelson (2023) stated that they are forced to pass on the additional costs to consumers in the form of higher prices for their goods. RAV often source their fruits from suppliers located in different regions, and transportation costs are a major factor in determining the final price of their products. The rising cost of shipping can significantly increase the cost of procuring goods, forcing RAVs to raise prices accordingly while the OAV may also source some of their goods from suppliers outside their immediate area, and they are similarly affected by rising shipping costs. This was illustrated in the study of Hu (2022) that the increased transportation expenses can reduce their profit margins or force them to adjust their pricing strategies.

To conclude, the table also shows the differences in their perceived reasons why prices increased. Occasional Ambulant Vendors (OAV) may not perceive weather conditions as a direct factor in price increases because the OAV often operate with limited inventory and focus on short-term sales. This means they are less likely to be affected by disruptions in supply chains caused by weather events, unlike Regular Ambulant Vendors (RAV) who maintain larger inventories and operate on a more consistent basis.

Cross- Case Analysis of the themes in Effects of Increased Prices of Commodities to RAV and OAV

Table 20 shows the cross-case analysis of the commonalties and differences of RAV and OAV in their perceived effects of the increased prices of commodities

Table 20. Cross- Case analysis of the commonalities and differences of RAV and OAV in their perceived effects of the increased prices of commodities

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
Income/ Profit loss due to: 1. Few products being sold due to high price 2.Spoilage	Changed the Purchasing behavior in order to save money due to lesser profits	Both RAV and OAV commonalities to the effects of the price increased is that both experienced the effect of profit loss	RAV sells fewer products and some it leads to spoilage while OAV it changes her purchasing behavior as an effect of price increased

The Table 20 shows the identified themes of the perceived effects of the inflation to RAV and OAV. Both vendors shared that they experienced the effect of increased price commodities is that they significantly loss a profit. This is explained in the study of Aldeguer (2016), in which he argued that ambulant vendors, who are self-employed individuals trading in public areas, face challenges such as loss of income when prices go up. This loss of income affects both regular and occasional ambulant vendors, impacting their livelihoods and ability to support their families

On the other hand, the difference in their perceived effects is when the prices of goods and commonalities increased is that RAV which operating on a more consistent basis and catering to a wider customer base, are more likely to experience reduced sales volumes when prices increase. Consumers may become more price-sensitive and seek out cheaper alternatives, leading to a decline in RAVs' overall sales while the OAV who catered to a more specific customer base and operating on a more sporadic basis, may face a different effect of price increases. Instead of reducing sales volumes, they may observe a change in their customers' purchasing buying attitude.

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV on how they combat inflation

This section shows the cross-case analysis of the identified themes RAV and OAV on how they combat inflation, and it shows the commonalities and differences of the themes. It includes the strategy on how they combat inflation, the way on how they combat and the difficulties and challenges they encountered while they are combating it.

Cross-Case analysis of RAV and OAV on their strategies on how they combat inflation

The table 21 below shows the commonalities of themes of the RAV and OAV in combating inflation and their differences.

Table 21 illustrates below that RAV and OAV shared the same themes of in combating inflation. They adopt various strategies to mitigate the impacts of inflation on their businesses. Ibáñez, Rugamas, Kohli, & Kuehl (2022) explained the importance of their actions will result to flexible policies that allow them to adjust prices based on inflation

rates. This flexibility can help them maintain a balance between covering costs and remaining competitive. The adoption of convenient strategies by Regular Ambulant Vendors and Occasional Ambulant Vendors is a proactive response to the challenges posed by inflation.

On the other hand, the difference in the themes is that only the OAV uses only online while the RAV utilize several strategies. RAV operate on a more regular basis and cater to a wider customer base, necessitating a more comprehensive strategy to address inflationary pressures. Webadmin (2023) explained that vendors need to maintain a diverse strategy to manage inventory effectively and implement cost-saving measures to remain competitive and profitable. In contrast, OAV with their occasional vending schedules and smaller customer base, have more flexibility in adapting their strategies to deal with inflation. They can focus on utilizing online platforms to reach a broader audience and supplement their physical vending activities, reducing the impact of inflation on their overall sales.

Table 22 Cross-Case analysis of the themes RAV and OAV in their strategies on how they combat inflation.

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
Adaptation Strategy to mitigate the impacts of inflation	Using online platform as an alternative	Adapt a convenient strategy to lessen the impacts of inflation	RAV uses adaptation strategies while OAV only utilize online platform

Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV on their ways to lessen the effect of inflation

This section provides the cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV on their ways to lessen the impacts of inflation.

Table 22 shows the comparison between RAV and OAV on their ways to combat and lessen the effect of the inflation. It shows here the commonalities and differences between the two. Both Regular Ambulant Vendors (RAV) and Occasional Ambulant Vendors (OAV) have adopted thriftier spending habits to manage the impact of rising costs and inflation. This shift in spending behavior is evident in their purchasing decisions, operational expenses, and overall approach to managing their businesses. Both RAVs and OAVs are demonstrating resilience and adaptability in the face of economic challenges. This was confirmed by the study of Olayemi (2023) in which according to him by adopting thriftier spending habits and exploring creative solutions, they can navigate the impacts of inflation

On the other hand, they vary in themes that the OAV is not only solely focus on saving money but also on being self-sufficient and managing cost efficient. While saving money is a crucial aspect of their operations, OAV also prioritize being able to operate independently and manage their expenses effectively. This approach confirmed by Williamson (2019) as it allows them to maintain control over their businesses, adapt to

changing market conditions, and ensure their long-term sustainability since their market strategy is not adept to everyday selling.

Table 22 Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV on their ways to lessen the effect of inflation

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
Frugality	Self-eliance and cost efficiency.	Both became thrifty and lessen their spending attitude	The focus of OAV is not solely on saving money but also on being self-sufficient and managing costs efficiently

Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV of the challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation

This section provides the cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV of the challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation.

Table 23. Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV of the challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
Reduced Purchasing behavior	Financial Struggles and Cost Management Additional Resources and Support Needs	Both RAV and OAV experiences financial difficulties as challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation	OAV need for more human resources and supports while RAV is a self supporting vendor that do not need another helper.

In the table 23, RAV and OAV shares the same themes in which is they experiences financial difficulties as challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation. According to Solis (2022), ambulant vendors experience financial difficulties as challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation. Rising food and fuel costs have forced them to ration their supplies or raise their prices on what some take for granted as convenient and affordable food, which puts their livelihood at stake. This was shown in the commonalities of the themes of RAV and OAV which they both experienced financial difficulties in combating inflation.

Furthermore, they have difference in their themes which comes to the challenges they face in combating inflation. In the case of OAV, she needs for more resources and supports while RAV is a self-supporting vendor. Considering that RAV operates as a daily fruit vendor near GPS Central School, he can manage his vending activities independently without requiring additional support or resources. On the other hand, OAV, being a clothing seller who participates in significant events, invariably requires assistance to run his business. This was explained in the study of Pu, Mehta, Naqvi, & Karim (2021) where they stated that OAV with their sporadic operations, limited resources, and smaller customer base, face challenges in sustaining their businesses and adapting to economic fluctuations. They often require additional support need for resources and support stems from their limited resources, sporadic operations, and smaller customer base. They require assistance in conducting her business in different areas. RAV on the other hand, are more self-supporting due to their established businesses, stable income streams, and adaptability.

Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV of the intervention of the government

This shows the cross- case analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV of the intervention of the government.

Table 24 Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV of the intervention of the government

RAV	OAV	Commonalities	Differences
NONE. The Vendor did not receive any kind of assistance from the government	No Financial Support for the Ambulant Vendor to address inflation	Both RAV and OAV did not receive any financial assistance from the government	No difference

The table 24 presented highlights the commonalities and distinctions in the themes concerning the government's intervention for both Regular Ambulant Vendors (RAV) and Occasional Ambulant Vendors (OAV). In examining the data, it is evident that neither of the vendors has received any form of financial assistance from the government.

Specifically, in the case of RAV, a clear assertion is made that no help has been received from government sources. This lack of assistance is not differentiated by type, encompassing various forms of support. Both vendors, either regular ambulant vendor or occasional ambulant vendor did not receive any financial assistance from the government.

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram for OAV & RAV

This schematic diagram presents the variables that encapsulates the essence of the previous themes within this diagram. It would serve as a comprehensive synthesis the commonalities and differences of Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV) and Occasional Ambulant Vendor. These graphical elements will suffice the relationship between various components through the use of this visual narrative that intricate the interconnectedness of the identified themes.

The extracted themes from the Regular Ambulant Vendor and Occasional Ambulant Vendor cases are systematically synthesized for a comprehensive analysis of their experiences, employed strategies, and the government's intervention. Utilizing symbols and diagrams, both sets of themes are visually represented in a cohesive, enclosed setting, forming a circle that facilitates the clear identification of commonalities related to inflation. Placed at the center of the diagram, the Ambulant vendors are focal points, signifying that they are the subjects of the identified themes. The external boxes surrounding the circle delineate distinctions between the two types of ambulant vendors, reflecting variations drawn from the themes extracted from their individual statements. This deliberate separation is driven by their unique preferences in navigating and strategizing responses to the impacts of inflation, as well as their distinct interactions with the government.

CASE 3: SAV (Salary-Based Ambulant Vendor)

The third participant is a 23-year-old salary-based vendor from Koronadal City, South Cotabato. For the past five years, he has been working in an “Aripahol” business, mashed sweetened cassava product. This particular food business has been around for nine years and has multiple branches in different locations within the city. He is paid on a daily basis with a specified time arrangement by owner. This means that they do not own the capital used to finance the goods and the necessary equipment. The vendor's stall is strategically located beside the City Health Office, right next to a bustling street crossing. He works for his cousin, whom he met under unfortunate circumstances – during an accident. This led him to aripahol vending, where he now helps his parents earn money for his school expenses. His workday begins at 7 in the morning and concludes at 7 in the evening. Rain or shine, he diligently works to sell food products to passersby. His dedication is further rewarded by the fact that the business owner provides him with all the necessary ingredients and equipment. Additionally, his unique work arrangement grants him incentives such as free boarding, food, water, and electricity, as his boss happens to be a relative.

Experience of Inflation by Salary-Based Ambulant Vendor (SAV)

This section provides the themes of occasional ambulant vendors in their experience during inflation period, their most difficult experience during inflation period, their perceived reason of the increased prices and commodities and their perceived effects of increased price and commodities.

Vending Experience of SAV During Inflation

Table 25 below shows the vending experience of SAV during inflation period with the themes, financial stability amidst increases price changes.

SAV talked about his experiences during inflation in which the themes that identified are relating to salary stability amidst increased price changes. Though SAV said that financial stability cannot be affected despite the price increase of gasoline and other products, saying that *“Ang income namon dati sa pagtaas sang gasolina kay daw same same lang man.”*. These findings rejected the claims of Bénabou. (2012), when he stated that Salary-based ambulant vendors, who receive a fixed wage rather than relying solely on commissions or sales, face additional challenges in maintaining financial stability during periods of inflation. This is because their income is not directly linked to their sales, making it difficult to adjust their earnings in response to price changes.

Table 25 Vending Experience of SAV During Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Ang income namon dati sa pagtaas sang gasolina kay daw same same lang man pero nag gamay medyo ang gabakal ka aripahol namon Bisan mag tass ang gasoline ang amon income kau di man maapektuhan same lang abi japon sweldo namon	Does not affect the income during the price increase of gasoline despite a small decrease of customers overall income will not be impacted.	Salary Stability Amidst Increased Price Changes

Most Difficult Experience of SAV during Inflation

This table shows the most difficult experience of SAV during inflation with the theme accident sill leading to financial loss.

SAV shared his most difficult experience during the inflation period that greatly contribute to income loss adding to the burden on inflation. Ambuko, Belik, Huang, & Timmermans (2014) concluded that accidents and spills in food preparation can lead to significant financial losses for various reasons, depending on the severity of the incident. In their research, they stated that spilled ingredients, spoiled food due to improper storage or handling, and unusable dishes all contribute to direct financial losses. The cost can be substantial, especially when dealing with expensive ingredients or large quantities of food.

Table Most Difficult Experience of SAV during Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
tung nabuhos akon binder, nabuhos ang lutuun ko ... ti wlaa ko kaluto dulaan gd kami satu benta nga dako.	Had an accident spilling resulting to the loss of sales	Accident spill leading to income loss

Perceived Reasons of SAV for the Increased prices and Commodities

Table 25 shows the perceived reasons of the SAV for the increased price and commodities which the identified themes are prices are going up primarily because of the high demand for the products.

Table 25 Perceived Reasons of SAV for the Increased prices of Commodities

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Ang ideya ko lang nga nagtaraas ang mga produkto kai nahilon, kusog kag dali lang mabakal ang mga produkto. Dali lang mabakal sang tao.	Prices are rising because there is significant demand for the products	High demand for the products

SAV talked about his perceived reasons on why the prices of commodities increased during the inflation period in which the concept and themes that are prices are going up primarily because of the high demand for the products as its themes. SAV said that his idea about inflation is due to demand for the products, stating, “*Ang ideya ko lang nga nagtaraas ang mga produkto kai nahilon, kusog kag dali lang mabakal ang mga produkto. Dali lang mabakal sang tao.*”.

It was explained by Gale (2015) that an increase in consumer demand, if not met with a proportional increase in supply, can create a shortage, leading to upward pressure on prices. The price of a good is determined by the interaction of supply and demand. In an open market, the price of a commodity naturally gravitates toward a point of balance, where the quantity supplied matches the quantity demanded. When the price is excessively high, a surplus of goods occurs, prompting producers to decrease the price to facilitate sales. Conversely, if the price is too low, a shortage arises, leading producers to increase prices to enhance profitability.

To support that claim Chen, & Simchi-Levi (2012) argued that SAV’s inclination towards attributing the rise in prices of goods and commodities to the Law of Supply and Demand underscores the significance of aligning consumer preferences with product

demand. Showing that the supply-demand imbalance in the dual-channel supply chain can have a significant impact on the optimal pricing and inventory strategies. When there is a supply shortage, the manufacturer and the retailer will both set higher prices and produce lower inventory levels. This is because they want to conserve their inventory and maximize their profits. Particularly relevant into the statement above about the relativity of consumer preferences and producers' abilities to meet those preferences, ultimately shaping the pricing dynamics in the market.

Perceived Effects of Increased prices of commodities to SAV

Table 26 shows the effects of the increased price and commodities to the SAV with the theme decline in the enthusiasm due reduced number of customers.

Table 26. Perceived Effects of Increased prices and commodities to SAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Naga bawas bawas si ate kung pila lang ka kilo ang gamiton kai basi di daw maubos ang binder. Galimit sya ... kay basi malugi daw sya	Restricting the quantity of items	Decreased number of products to sell

SAV talked about his experiences on how it affects him on increased prices and commodities during the inflation period in which the theme is reducing the products to sell.. SAV said that “*Naga bawas bawas si ate kung pila lang ka kilo ang gamiton kai basi di daw maubos ang binder. Galimit sya ... kay basi malugi daw sya*”, showing that one of the effects is

SAV’s claims may be explained by Mcleod (2023) as he pointed out that preferences toward the business are crucial due to the direct correlation between customer numbers, revenue generation, and the overall satisfaction of the business owner and employees. It becomes uncertain when a business has fewer customers, affecting both employee motivation and the business's future outlook. This not only influences individual productivity but also links to the physiological and safety needs of customers and vendors. A reduced customer base can lead to income decline for vendors, affecting their ability to meet basic physiological needs and causing financial stress. This financial uncertainty extends to potential customers concerned about their own stability.

Salary-Based Ambulant Vendor on combating inflation

This section provides the themes on how the SAV combats inflation. It includes its strategies, ways and the challenges he faces while combating inflation.

Strategy of SAV to Combat Inflation

This section shows on the themes of SAV strategy in combating inflation which is adapting to geographical mobility to gain income.

Table Strategy of SAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
<p>Nag initiative ko nga lako lako o gilibud, para man maka bawi man sa amon nga sales.</p> <p>Ginlibod namon sya bisan asa kay syempre dako tung nadula sa paghula ko ka binder para daw ma ka bawi bawi man kami satu kay mahal mahal mga presyo satu</p>	<p>Initiated selling or promotional efforts to different places to recover lost sales</p>	<p>Proactively engaged in selling or promoting in different places</p>

SAV talked about his strategies on how he combats inflation by proactively engaged in selling or promoting in different places. SAV acknowledged that involving in roaming around the town and sells the product can gain income; he stated “*Nag initiative ko nga lako lako o gilibud, para man maka bawi man sa amon nga sales*”, and supporting his thought by adding, “*Ginlibod namon sya bisan asa*”.

This was confirmed in the study of Halton (2023), it was identified that the case of SAV in order for the income to increase, it needs to adapt with the current state of their customer thus, engaging in relocating their stalls. Geographical mobility shares a lot of advantages in acquiring specific goals. By expanding into new markets, vendors can reach a wider customer base and increase their sales, and often associated with higher productivity and economic output. Implying that it makes it easier for vendors to adapt to geographical mobility, as they can continue to work with their clients even if they move to a new location. As the business owner do not have to pay commissions or fees to their clients reducing the cost of the expenses. This reduction in costs can make it easier for vendors to adapt to geographical mobility, as they can afford to move to new locations without sacrificing their income.

Ways of SAV to Combat Inflation

Table 27 shows the themes of SAV on his ways to combat inflation by creation of products for lower risk of income loss.

SAV talked about his ways that he utilizes on how he combat inflation with the themes that identified is limited creation of products for possible lower risk of income loss. SAV emphasized that the way given by his owner to prevent higher risk of income loss is limiting the production of his products, stating that “*Gina control ka amo ko ang ginahatag*”

nya nga binder.... damo abi ang balinhuy tapos gamay lang ang sang tao o customer ti damo ang mabilin.”.

This claim was supported by Lele (2019), stating that the statement of SAV situates in the model of the framework of salary-based vendor management, as highlighted. The relationship between clients and vendors is crucial for overseeing products and reducing the risk of losing income and expanding the cost of expenses. Ambulant Vendors benefit by having flexibility in choosing and customizing their offerings to meet customer needs. This flexibility helps vendors control their products, avoiding potential income loss. Overall, it is a great solution for businesses, aligning with the goals of both clients and vendors. It serves as a strategy to help both parties control their products and reduce the risk of losing income.

Table 27. Ways of SAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Gina control ka amo ko ang ginahatag nya nga binder.... damo abi ang balinhuy tapos gamay lang ang sang tao o customer ti damo ang mabilin.	Controlling the products that are given by the owner to the vendor to prevent higher risk of income loss	Limited creation of products for possible lower risk of income loss

Challenges and difficulties of SAV to Combat Inflation

This section shows the themes of SAV on the challenges and difficulties he faced while combating Inflation which the identified themes compromising safety.

Table 28. Challenges and Difficulties of SAV to Combat Inflation

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Mga ido nga maglagas sa imo	Being chased by stray animals, such as dogs, when peddling the products	Compromising safety Customers lack engagement
Mga tao nga di ma approaches sa imo mga Wala balak mag bakal sang produkto	People paying no attention to you No intention in buying the products	
Door to door nga pamaligya tas hambalon nga wala tao pero my ara man	Rejection customers in the context of direct selling at their doorstep.	

SAV’s strategies to combat inflation is to sells his products in the different parts of City of Koronadal. One difficulty he faced is his safety during his peddling activities

because of strays dogs in the street of Koronadal, he stated that “*mga ido nga maglagas sa imo*”, he also shared that the challenging thing he encountered aside from the dogs is the lack of engagement of possible customers, he said with disappointment, “*MayMga tao nga di ma approach sa imo*”, and “*Wala balak mag bakal sang produkto*”, as well as saying, “*Door to door nga pamaligya tas hambalon nga wala tao pero my ara man*”. This was confirmed in the article titled “Mobilizing the Streets: The Role of Food Vendors in Urban Life” by Allison & Rohel .(2021). It talks about how street vendors, who sell food on the streets, face many challenges, as being posit by the SAV in his experience into peddling activities. One big problem is the risk of getting hurt by stray animals. It highlighted those challenges faced by vendors are important in cities because they provide affordable and easy-to-get food for people. But even though they help a lot, street vendors have a lot of problems. They might be bothered by the police, get fines for using public space, and even face danger from stray animals.

Government Interventions provided to Salary-based Ambulant Vendor

This section provides the identified themes of salary-based ambulant vendor in the government intervention provided by the state. This includes the assistance and any forms of help from the government.

Government Interventions provided to Salary-based Ambulant Vendor

This section shows the themes of the intervention of the government which identified that there is no financial aid for the ambulant vendor from the government.

Table 29 Intervention of the Government to SAV

Significant Statements	Formulated Meanings	Themes
Wala gd... Pero sa amon nga amo may ara.	I did not receive financial help from the government Only the owner receives the interventions of the government but to the ambulant vendors received none	No Financial Aid

SAV talked about not having financial aid as the the intervention of the government. SAV negatively said that, “*Wala gd.*”, and vividly followed his statement by saying, “*Pero sa amon nga amo may ara.*”. Despite the fact that SAV emphasized that there is no financial intervention from the government, during the interview, the researchers notably observed that there is a traffic enforcer, regulating the traffic beside his stall. It means that there is a security assistance provided to him in the form of traffic enforcer to conduct his business peacefully. This was supported by the Modern Liberalism as it promotes own will to combat the existing phenomena but providing a minimal intervention. In this case, SAV do not receive financial assistance from the government but received a security assistance from the LGU of City of Koronadal.

Schematic Diagram of the Themes of SAV

The themes were summarized in the context of the Salary-based ambulant vendor during the inflation and put it into content of schematic diagram. The primary contributors of inflation are put into one setting emphasizing that high demands for products and increased price for gasoline was the cause of inflation. It was also synthesized that the salary-based vendor enthusiasm declines because of the reduced numbers of the customers and showing that financial stabilization can be achieved because of the customers preferences for the product that could led to loyalty for the business. However, these themes were recognized by the vendor that it could not affect him due to the nature of his work, having a fixed salary. Two bolded arrows are used because it signifies that despite of the nature of vendor's work, it still provided various alternatives to gain income for the business. The vendor engages in peddling activities as well as moving to different places to acquire income. But challenges are contextualized within the strategies of the vendors to identify the leading factors why certain challenges occurred. Curly brace is used to separate the government aids and programs since it acts as an independent variable and denoting to the interaction of vendor towards it. Yet, it was clear that due to inequitable distribution of aids and programs provided, and lack of initiative prevented the vendor to abstain such aids and program.

Figure 4 Schematic Diagram of the Themes of SAV

Cross – Case Analysis of in their experience during inflation: RAV, OAV and SAV

This section shows the cross – case analysis of RAV and OAV and SAV on how they experience during inflation, on their most difficult experiences, their perceived reasons on the increase price on commodities and the perceive effects of the inflation

Table 30 shows the cross-case analysis of the RAV and OAV vs SAV of their experiences during inflation.

Table 30. Cross – Case Analysis of RAV, OAV and SAV of their vending experiences during inflation

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
OAV nature of business does not constantly relied on the availability of products, and they are experiencing financial constraints while the products of the business of RAV relies also on the availability and unavailability of the supply	Salary stability amidst increased price changes	The commonalities between the RAV, OAV and SAV is that they experienced negative effects on their vending business when price fluctuations or price changes occur	Salary Based Vendor has salary stability despite increased price changes while the RAV and OAV experienced financial difficulties due to inflation brought by several factors

RAV, OAV and SAV shared the commonalities and differences in their themes pertaining to their experiences during inflation. They shared the commonalities of their experiences as they all experience negative consequences especially in business field. This was explained in the study of Lingen (2023) he said that business owners like ambulant vendors, involved in purchasing and selling goods, directly feel the effects of inflation through higher procurement costs. This includes increased expenses for transportation, fuel, and raw materials, resulting in elevated product prices. These fluctuations impact profit margins, customer demand, and overall business competitiveness. On a smaller scale, OAVs also contend with price fluctuations, facing heightened costs for supplies, transportation, and storage, leading to increased product prices. Their flexibility in adjusting prices may be limited by competition and market forces, making it challenging to fully pass on the cost increase to consumers. As consumers, SAVs experience the consequences of price fluctuations, grappling with rising costs for essential goods and services such as food, transportation, housing, and utilities.

Table 30 shows that while RAV and OAV have experienced financial difficulties during inflation due to several factors, SAV was hardly hit by inflation because his salary was stable. SAV typically benefit from a relatively higher level of financial stability when compared to business owners like RAVs and OAVs. The primary contributor to this stability is the consistent and steady nature of SAVs' income. Unlike RAVs and OAVs, whose earnings are directly tied to the profitability of their businesses, SAVs often receive a fixed or more predictable income.

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV, OAV and SAV on their most difficult experience during inflation.

Table 31 shows the cross – case analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV in their most difficult experience during inflation. It shows the commonalities and differences of their most difficult experience.

It shows the similarities of themes of RAV, OAV and SAV in their most difficult experience during inflation is experiencing being exacerbated by the economic challenges brought about by inflation. This was further elaborated by Krugman & Wells (2018), that the economic challenges brought about by inflation, therefore, act as a compounding factor for vendors of various types. It influences their decision-making, pricing strategies, and overall business competitiveness, adding another layer of complexity to the already demanding nature of their entrepreneurial endeavors.

Moreover, table 31 also shows the differences in terms of their most difficult experiences which is RAV and OAV facing business and economic challenges in inflation. RAV struggles with setting prices and keeping customers satisfied, while OAV's problem is adjusting to changes in purchasing power on the other hand, SAV dealing with the financial consequences of an unexpected loss, indicating a specific and possibly unforeseen financial challenge. RAV and OAV is directly engaged in their business that is why their most difficult experience can be associated into their cost-profit margin. According to Heracleous (2014), for both regular and occasional ambulant vendors, the day-to-day difficulties revolve around the financial challenges and difficulties of procurement costs, pricing strategies, and the constant fluctuations in market dynamics. The relentless balancing act between expenses, such as the costs of goods and transportation, and the pursuit of revenue becomes a central theme in their experiences.

While the experiences of salary-based vendors diverge from the cost-profit dynamics. In the same article of Heracleous (2014) he argued that their most challenging moments extend beyond the realms of the traditional business model. The difficulties faced by salary-based vendors may encompass aspects such as job security, workplace dynamics, and market challenges that transcend the direct correlation to monetary gains and losses. To conclude, the SAV most difficult experience can be associated into something else aside from cost-profit.

Table 31. Cross – Case Analysis of RAV, OAV and SAV on their most difficult experience during inflation.

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Both RAV and OAV most difficult experience during inflation are Dissatisfaction and Reducing customers. RAV difficult experience is to increase the price of the fruits he sells while the OAV it changed his attitude in terms of purchasing behavior.	SAV's most difficult experience is when he has an accident spill that resulted in income loss.	The challenging experiences faced by different types of vendors exacerbated by the negative financial challenges	RAV and OAV facing business and economic challenges in inflation. RAV struggles with setting prices and keeping customers satisfied, while OAV's problem is adjusting to changes in purchasing power. On the other hand, SAV dealing with the income loss due to accidental spill.

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV, OAV and SAV on their perceived reasons why price on commodities increased

Table 32 shows the cross-case analysis of the RAV and OAV vs SAV on how they perceived reasons why prices on commodities increased. It shows the commonalities and differences on their perceived reasons.

Table 32 cross-case analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on how they perceived the reasons why the cost of price and commodities get high

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Both RAV and OAV shared that the cost of fuel and shipping process is perceived as a reason why prices of	SAV perceived that the reasons why prices are going up primarily because of the high demand for the products	Both RAV and OAV, as well as SAV, recognize that external factors is the reasons why the prices increased	RAV and OAV share the perception that the cost of fuel and the shipping process contribute to the rise in commodity prices.

commodities increase OAV does not equate weather condition as factor why prices increased			While SAV perceives that the primary reason for the increase in prices is the high demand for the products.
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It is shown that RAV, OAV and SAV shared common themes on the perceived external factors for the price increase being experienced perceive reasons why the prices increased. Acknowledging the influence of external factors, Boamong (2022), explained that RAVs, OAVs, and SAVs seek ways to adapt and manage their finances within their spheres of control. They explore strategies to reduce costs, diversify income streams, and prioritize essential expenses. In the differences of their themes, RAV and OAV share the perception that the cost of fuel and the shipping process contributes to the rise in commodity prices. While SAV perceives that the primary reason for the increase in prices is the high demand for the products. RAVs and OAVs have a more nuanced understanding of the factors contributing to rising commodity prices due to their direct involvement in the supply chain. SAVs' perception may be more focused on the demand side because he does not own the business entirely.

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV, OAV and SAV on the effects of the inflation

Table 33 shows the cross-case analysis of the RAV and OAV vs SAV on the effects of the inflation. It shows the commonalities and differences in the effects of the inflation.

Table 33 Cross – Case Analysis of RAV, OAV and SAV on the perceived effects of the inflation

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Both RAV and OAV commonalities to the effects of the price increased is that both experienced the effect of profit loss RAV sells fewer products and some it leads to spoilage while OAV it changes his purchasing power attitude as an effect of price increased	Reduced number of products	RAV, OAV and SAV shared the same themes which is Negative consequences stemming from the increased prices.	RAV and OAV experience the effects of profit loss and unstable income while SAV limiting the products to be sold in the market.

RAV, OAV and SAV answered a common theme for their answers on what is the effect of the inflation. They shared theme of negative consequences stemming from increased prices affect these vendors in various ways. It can impact their profit margins, overall income, and ability to adapt to changing market conditions. The specific challenges each type of vendor faces may vary, but the common thread is the potential negative impact of rising prices on their livelihoods and businesses.

This was explained by Friedline, Chen, & Morrow (2020), who argued that the RAVs and OAVs face profit loss and unstable income due to their direct exposure to rising costs and limited flexibility in pricing. SAVs, on the other hand, limits his products to be sold in market. He sells fewer to avoid potential income loss and the fact that any unsold products cannot be sell again and it will go to waste.

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on how they combat inflation

This section contains the cross-case analysis of RAV-OAV and SAV on how they combat inflation, the strategy, ways and difficulty in combating it.

Cross-Case Analysis of the themes of RAV – OAV and SAV on Strategy they use to combat the inflation

Table 34 shows cross-case analysis of the themes of RAV and OAV vs SAV on the strategy they used to combat inflation.

The table shows how RAV, OAV and SAV shared the commonalities on how they combat inflation. They shared that they all acknowledge the need for flexibility and innovation to navigate challenges brought by inflation. This claim was supported by Thompson (2023) Regular Ambulant Vendors (RAV), Occasional Ambulant Vendors (OAV), and Salary-Based Ambulant Vendors (SAV) all recognize the need for flexibility and innovation to adapt to the challenges posed by inflation. While they face different economic circumstances and financial pressures, they all share a common understanding that adaptability and creativity are crucial for navigating economic uncertainties. They also shared the differences of their themes. RAVs, OAVs, and SAVs employ different strategies to combat inflation, tailored to their unique circumstances and economic realities. RAVs focus on product diversification, inventory management, cost-saving measures, and customer engagement. OAVs leverage online platforms, explore alternative income streams, and build strong customer relationships. SAVs consider geographical mobility in vending, negotiate wage adjustments, review spending habits, and invest in upskilling or reskilling. By adapting their approaches and embracing innovation, all three groups can navigate economic challenges and maintain financial stability (Kramer, 2023).

Table 34 Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on Strategies they use to combat the inflation

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Adapt a convenient strategy to lessen the impacts of inflation RAV uses various strategies while OAV only utilize online platform	Proactively engaged in selling or promoting in different places	RAV, OAV and SAV similarities is that they all acknowledge the need for flexibility and innovation to navigate challenges brought by inflation.	RAV uses several strategies to combat inflation and OAV uses only the online platform to combat inflation while the SAV is adapting geographical mobility in vending to combat inflation

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on the ways they used to combat inflation

Table 35 shows cross-case analysis of the themes of RAV - OAV and SAV on the ways they used to combat inflation. It shows the commonalities and differences on their ways.

Table 35 Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on the ways they used to combat inflation.

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Both became thrifty and frugal to lessen their spending attitude The focus of OAV is not solely on saving money but also on being self-sufficient and managing costs efficiently	Limited creation of products for lower risk of income loss	RAV, OAV and SAV exerts efforts to manage Ccsts and income	RAV and OAV take proactive steps to handle inflation by being thrifter and pursuing self-sufficient strategies while SAV focuses on minimizing risks and safeguarding income by cutting costs and seeking wage adjustments

The table 35 shows the commonalities of RA, OAV and SAV in their themes that tackles their ways to combat inflation. Among their ways they shared one common answer while they exert efforts to manage costs and income. They make efforts to manage costs and income in ways that align with their unique challenges and circumstances. This was backed by the study of Hashemi-Pour & Fogarty (2023). These efforts involve a

combination of strategic sourcing, marketing, sales optimization, and financial planning to enhance overall financial resilience and sustainability

The table also shows the differences in the ways on how they combat inflation. According to them, RAV and OAV take proactive steps to handle inflation by being thrifter and pursuing self-sufficient strategies while SAV focuses on minimizing risks and safeguarding income by cutting costs and seeking wage adjustments. RAV and OAV adopt thrifty practices, pursue self-sufficient strategies, and focus on customer-centric approaches to proactively manage inflation. SAV, on the other hand, prioritize cost-cutting measures, engage in wage negotiations, and invest in upskilling or reskilling to minimize risks and safeguard their income in the face of economic pressures.

Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on the challenges and difficulties in combating inflation

Table 36 shows cross-case analysis of the themes of RAV - OAV and SAV on the challenges and difficulties in combating inflation. It shows the commonalities and differences in their difficulties and challenges they faced.

Ambulant vendor shared the commonalities in their challenges which is the adapting to changing consumer behavior. Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV), Occasional Ambulant Vendor (OAV), and Salary-Based Ambulant Vendor (SAV) face the challenge of adapting to changing consumer behavior in combating inflation.). This difficulty is in agreement with the study of Garg (2022) who states that understanding the dynamics of consumer behavior, adapting their strategies accordingly, and embracing innovation, vendors can deal the challenges posed by inflation and maintain their financial stability and resilience.

The differences in their answers in the themes of the challenges and difficulties also shown in the table 41. RAV and OAV encountered financial challenges while grappling with inflation, whereas SAV confronted challenges related to safety and a lack of customer engagement in their vending business. Regular Ambulant Vendor (RAV) and Occasional Ambulant Vendor (OAV) primarily face financial challenges due to inflation, while Salary-Based Ambulant Vendor (SAV) encounter challenges related to safety and customer engagement in their vending businesses.

Table 36. Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV on the challenges and difficulties in combating inflation

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Both RAV and OAV experiences financial difficulties as challenges and difficulties they face when they combat inflation OAV need for more resources and supports while RAV is a self-supporting vendor	Compromising Security Customers lack engagement	RAV, OAV and SAV shared the commonalities in their themes which is the challenge to the adapting to changing consumer behavior.	RAV and OAV encountered financial challenges while grappling with inflation, whereas SAV confronted challenges related to safety and a lack of customer engagement in their vending business.

Cross – Case analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV in intervention of the government

The table shows only the commonalities of the themes which is all the three types of vendors regardless of what kind they are or what products they are selling they did not receive any financial aid or financial assistance of any kind from the government. This was explained in the article of Agnes (2021) titled, Moral Politics of Sidewalk Vending: The Struggle between the City Authorities and Sidewalk Vendors of the City of Manila, he argued that authorities perceived the vendors as undisciplined and undesirable illegals that is why it is only once in a while a financial assistance from the government provided to the ambulant vendors. In spite the fact that there is no financial assistance received by the vendors, as the researchers observed during their interview, all vendors receive security assistance from the government to conduct their vending business peacefully.

Table 37 Cross – Case Analysis of RAV and OAV vs SAV in intervention of the government

RAV and OAV	SAV	Commonalities	Differences
Both RAV and OAV did not receive any financial assistance from the government RAV has not gotten any help from the government, and OAV, while not ruling out other types of assistance, lacks financial aid to	No Financial Aid for the ambulant vendor from the government because of inequitable distribution of government assistance	No Intervention coming from the Government especially the financial assistance	No difference

tackle challenge	inflation			
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Schematic Diagram of the Themes of RAV & OAV vs SAV

The schematic diagram illustrates the commonalities and differences of RAV and OAV to SAV. Their commonalities are set in the circle, sectioned by their experiences, strategies, and government interventions while the differences of RAV and OAV to SAV are presented in the boxes outside the circle. The concepts on the upper section in the circle are the shared experiences of the three ambulant vendors where they all experienced price fluctuation, profit loss and other challenging experiences brought about by inflation. They also agreed there are external factors that contributed to the price increase, and this is why negative consequences have manifested. However, they also differed on some aspects such as financial difficulties of RAV and OAV where they struggled with setting prices, customer satisfaction and changes in purchasing behavior which contributed to their profit loss and unstable income. SAV, meanwhile, had thought that price increase was caused by high demand of products and despite experiencing profit loss, its impact was minimized due because of a stable income.

As for the strategies employed to mitigate the effects of inflation, the three vendors acknowledged the need for flexibility and innovation and have exerted efforts in managing costs and income in response to the changing consumer behavior. They differed, however, in their methods of adaptation where RAV and OAV utilized online platform, have been thriftier and pursued self-sufficient strategies in facing the financial challenges. On the other hand, SAV have adapted geographical mobility, cut costs, and wage adjustment despite the challenges of safety and lack of customer. For government aid and programs, the three ambulant vendors have similar experience of not receiving any financial assistance.

Figure 5. Schematic Diagram of the Themes of RAV & OAV vs SAV

Formulated Conceptual Framework

The variables present in this diagram are all related to the three identified classifications of Ambulant Vendors, as described in earlier sections of this paper. After the collection of data from the participants, these findings become the basis for constructing the grand-conceptual framework of the study. These variables reflect the interconnected aspects relevant to the research problems. One variable is dependent on the other, since all of the answer given by the participants are extracted to make the themes for the study, thus, also making it the determinant of what are the results of their actions. All experiences of the Ambulant vendors are reflected by the strategies done by them. The diagram shows the fluctuation of the variables just how inflation works as it is. Each variable has shown interrelatedness, indicating how ambulant vendors addressed inflation through various methods and strategies. The negative impact of inflation to the ambulant vendors are shown to be pulled down, since their experiences are all negative making it harder for them to cope up from the adverse effect of the inflation. Their situation became worsen because of minimal assistance from the government. It can be seen that

the government intervention is being drag down, not all the way from the bottom since this intervention may take the form of public safety measures, the implementation of occupational taxes for those unable to afford city business permits, and the freedom to engage in vending activities without discrimination. Additionally, their presence was acknowledged by contributing to the city's economy without hindrance from the micro-business owners.

Despite the vendors' limited awareness of these interventions, they employ strategic methods to cope with the effects of inflation, turning to various platforms as alternative means including, online platform, business mobility to acquire more customer and income, Thrifty behavior of the vendor, and lastly is by putting limited products needed to sell. This showcases the vendors' resilience and adaptability in the face of economic challenges, even when the full extent of government involvement may not be fully comprehended by them.

Conclusions

The study primarily aimed to describe the experiences the phenomenon combating inflation as experienced by the ambulant vendors in the City of Koronadal, specifically their experiences in inflation, on how they combat inflation and what are the interventions of the government provided to them.

On Their experiences on inflation. Based on the result, ambulant vendors experienced price fluctuations, economic challenges, and negative consequences stemming from increased prices that affect their livelihood. Price fluctuations have a significant impact on the livelihoods of ambulant vendors. This is due to the fact that ambulant vendors often operate on thin margins and are therefore very sensitive to changes in the price of goods. As a result, price fluctuations can lead to economic challenges for ambulant vendors, such as decreased profits and even losses. These experiences are common among the three types of ambulant vendors although, it seems like between those who receive salary from the business owner and those vendors who finance their own business, the latter are more likely to be greatly affected. It is also interesting to note that the kind of products being sold by the ambulant vendors could be a factor to their experience of inflation.

On how the ambulant vendors combat inflation. As the inflation surges, ambulant vendors must do something to combat it. Based on the result, ambulant vendors combat inflation by using several strategies especially utilizing online platforms, changing their buying behavior and wage adjustments. Ambulant vendors are being proactive in dealing with inflation, the need to earn profit in order to sustain and an income in order to progress their business. This shows how the ambulant vendors are becoming resilient in times of adversities. But humans as they are, in combating inflation they face several difficulties such as lack of engagement and safety risk. These challenges can hinder their efforts to lessen the negative effects of the inflation.

On the interventions provided by the government to the ambulant vendors.

Interventions, assistance, and aid from the government is necessary. It is a way of showing that the government is for the poor and for marginalized. Based on the results, all three ambulant vendors did not receive any financial assistance or aid coming from the government. However, assistance does not only emanate from financial aid or giving money incentives. It may also be in a form of providing security, public welfare, and many others. Ambulant vendors are the sectors in the society considered to be informal settlers. They do not pay taxes, secure business permit and pay rent. Despite that, the government allowed them to engage and operate their business. The Local Government Unit (LGU) of the City of Koronadal, notably, ensures the security and well-being of the ambulant vendors by consistently carrying out patrols in their designated areas. This demonstrates that, despite the lack of financial aid, the focus remains on providing security assistance to maintain peace, allowing individuals to carry out their businesses and jobs without disruption.

Recommendations

The results of the study implied that while ambulant vendors have different nature in vending shared same experiences that have a negative effect on their livelihood and living. Hence, it is important to collaborate with local governments to advocate policies and programs to help lessen the negative effects of inflation. In addition, regular monitoring by the government is needed to the condition of the ambulant vendors who are experiencing to the negative effects of the inflation. Lastly, to make easy for the ambulant vendors to apply for such assistance or interventions the government should not require a lot of administrative documents that seems impossible to comply especially for the ambulant vendors.

Also, based on the study, results are implicitly stated how ambulant vendors becomes resilient, adapting strategies especially in online selling to help them combat inflation. Despite the fact that ambulant vendors employ several ways and strategies to mitigate the impacts of the inflation, the government must facilitate a workshops or trainings to help them manage their business more efficiently in time of inflation. LGU should also provide trainings and support to ambulant vendors using the technology in a more useful manner in order for the ambulant vendor to connect with customers and expand their customer base. Lastly, that ambulant vendors should create cooperatives or associations to strengthen their collective voice and advocate for their needs.

Ambulant vendors directly stated that there is no assistance in any form that they receive. Granted that there is a security assistance provided by the government to conduct their business in a peaceful way, they did not consider this as a form of assistance. The government especially the LGU should educate more the ambulant vendors that assistance and intervention come in many forms. Financial assistance is just one of them. In addition, government should conduct a symposium why inflation happens and why it is an inevitable phenomenon to happen in the community and lastly, LGU of

Koronadal should give a financial assistance to the ambulant vendors to help them finance their business smoothly and efficiently.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The participation of ambulant vendors in the study was entirely voluntary, with a strict adherence to confidentiality protocols throughout. Measures were meticulously implemented to ensure the anonymity of participants, including the removal of names during data analysis and the assignment of numerical identifiers to prevent bias. Prior to conducting interviews, researchers followed a structured protocol and obtained informed consent from each participant, respecting their rights and privacy. The consent form outlined participants' rights to accept or decline interviews and detailed confidentiality provisions to protect their privacy. Throughout the study, the researchers prioritized the well-being of participants and maintained integrity in reporting findings and quotes, fostering a respectful and honest environment.

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REFERENCES

- Addeh, Olusola, Chimezie, & Shuuya, (2022). The Impact of Inflation Rate on Private Consumption Expenditure and Economic Growth—Evidence from Ghana. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 10(04), 1601–1646. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2022.104084>
- Ailawadi,., Neslin & Gedenk, (2001). Pursuing the Value-Conscious Consumer: Store Brands versus National Brand Promotions. *Journal of Marketing*, 65(1), 71–89. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.65.1.71.18132>
- Aldeguer, (2016). A Study of Training Needs of Ambulant Vendors within the University Belt Area, City of Manila (Philippines). *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2413082>
- Allison & Rohel, (2021). Mobilizing the streets: the role of food vendors in urban life. *Food, Culture, and Society*, 24(1), 2–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15528014.2020.1860454>
- Andres & Hernando (n.d). *Inflation and Economic Growth; Some Evidence for the OECD countries*. Retrieve from:chrome extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.bis.org/publ/confp04.pdf
- Antwi-Boampong, Boison., Doumbia., Boakye, Osei-Fosua, L., & Sarbeng. (2022). Factors affecting port users' behavioral intentions to adopt financial technology (Fintech) in ports in Sub-Saharan Africa: A case of ports in Ghana. *FinTech*, 1(4), 362–375. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fintech1040027>
- Atnafu, & Balda, (2018). The impact of inventory management practice on firms' competitiveness and organizational performance: Empirical evidence from micro and small enterprises in Ethiopia. *Cogent Business & Management*, 5(1), 1503219. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2018.1503219>

- Bénabou, R. (2012). Tax and Education Policy in a Heterogeneous-Agent Economy: What Levels of Redistribution Maximize Growth and Efficiency? *Econometrica*, 70(2), 481–517. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0262.00293>
- Braun & Clarke. (2021). A worked example of Braun and Clarke’s approach to reflexive thematic analysis. *Quality & Quantity*, 56(3), 1391–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01182-y>
- Chen, & Simchi-Levi, D. (2012). Dynamic pricing and inventory management of a dual-channel supply chain under different power structures. *Management Science*, 58(5), 946-962.
- Chopra, S. (2014). *Reducing the risk of supply chain disruptions*. MIT Sloan Management Review. https://sloanreview.mit.edu/article/reducing-the-risk-of-supply-chain-disruptions/?fbclid=IwAR36_xSNp5g8k8bH9jpX6vfl3nsHSfa6ZhFiZoQZ-A0dYwJGowoT3fllMDE
- Dhar, R. (2022, August 22). *How does inflation change consumer behavior?* Yale Insights. <https://insights.som.yale.edu/insights/how-does-inflation-change-consumer-behavior?fbclid=IwAR1znSamE97BUxHvx3JQSoD6p1sZKgjRIGCxLkWuJ93vCVxbJkEBPXsBvto>
- Fernando, J. (2023). Inflation: What It Is, How It Can Be Controlled, and Extreme Examples. Investopedia. Retrived from: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/inflation.asp>
- Friedline, T., Chen, Z., & Morrow, S. (2020). Families’ Financial Stress & Well-Being: The Importance of the Economy and Economic Environments. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 42(S1), 34–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10834-020-09694-9>
- Gale, D. (2015). The law of supply and demand. *MATHEMATICA SCANDINAVICA*, 3, 155–169. <https://doi.org/10.7146/math.scand.a-10436>
- Garg, G. (2022). *Consumer Behavior and Trends: How to Improve your Business Strategy*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/consumer-behavior-trends-how-improve-your-business-strategy-garg?fbclid=IwAR1znSamE97BUxHvx3JQSoD6p1sZKgjRIGCxLkWuJ93vCVxbJkEBPXsBvto>
- Gu, Ślusarczyk, Hajizada, Kovalyova, & Sakhbieva, A. (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on online consumer purchasing behavior. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(6), 2263–2281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16060125>
- Halton, C. (2023). *Geographical Labor mobility: Overview, pros and cons, FAQ*. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/geographical-mobility-of-labor.asp#toc-what-is-occupational-labor-mobility>
- Hashemi-Pour, C., & Fogarty, S. (2023). *strategic sourcing*. ERP. <https://www.techtarget.com/searcherp/definition/strategic-sourcing?fbclid=IwAR1eT9oJYokJFNRIorD96mFT-Az9B4Z-e52Dst8lZotvtQHAXmAfF4OsD14>

- Hayes, A. (2023). *Understanding purchasing power and the consumer price index*. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/purchasingpower.asp>
- Hayes, A. (2023). What is Revenue? Definition, Formula, Calculation, and Example. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/r/revenue.asp>
- Heracleous, L. (2014). *The Globe: Singapore Airlines' Balancing Act*. Harvard Business Review. https://hbr.org/2010/07/the-globe-singapore-airlines-balancing-act?fbclid=IwAR0xuLTsFZf5aDCM7ijS-sMUi9ISUGLYHaCw4tk3pRv1u8L323laey_BgXI
- Homes, L. (2022). 3 Major Contributing Factors for Inflation Rate in the Philippines. Lumina Homes. Retrieved from: <https://www.lumina.com.ph/newsand-blogs/blogs/3-major-contributing-factors-for-inflation-rate-in-the-philippines/>
- Ibáñez, P., Rugamas, R. G., Kohli, S., & Kuehl, E. (2022). *How to deal with price increases in this inflationary market*. McKinsey & Company. https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/operations/our-insights/how-to-deal-with-price-increases-in-this-inflationary-market?fbclid=IwAR1NbTiz3Q3N8h49pB4ykwDm06dpMjFrReFO__rK8dfhj1BURq1gxl1dU
- International Monetary Fund [IMF]. (2022). World Economic Outlook. IMF. Retrieved April 10, 2023, from <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO>
- Jaishankar, & Sujatha. (2016). A Study on Problems Faced by the Street Vendors in Tiruchirappalli City. *SSRG International Journal of Economics and Management Studies*, 3(9). <https://www.internationaljournalsrg.org/IJEMS/2016/Volume3-Issue9/IJEMS-V3I5P119.pdf>
- Kenton, W. (2023). *Cost Push Inflation: When it occurs, definition, and causes*. Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/costpushinflation.asp>
- Kirshner, J. (2011). The Political Economy of Low Inflation. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 15(1), 41–70. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-6419.00132>
- Kramer, L. (2023). *How do governments fight inflation?* Investopedia. <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/111314/what-methods-can-government-use-control-inflation.asp>
- Luong, P. (2023). *Hanoi's Roving Street Vendors : Navigating Cultural and Urban Transformations in the Digital Age*. DIVA. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1798736&dswid=3232>
- Mankiw, & Reis. (2016). Sticky Information versus Sticky Prices: A Proposal to Replace the New Keynesian Phillips Curve. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 117(4), 1295–1328. <https://doi.org/10.1162/003355302320935034>
- Mcleod, S., PhD. (2023). Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/maslow.html#Applications-Examples>
- Mecalux. (n.d.). *How inflation affects the supply chain*. https://www.mecalux.com/blog/supply-chain-inflation?fbclid=IwAR3bD57Qn5owtM8aZ-_Mq0hh0NcF8-I5AFJK8ZvRBzEMIUqMEGxsZ633N8g

- Nelson, F. (2023). Effects of Inflation on Business: The Good and The Bad. Oracle NetSuite. <https://www.netsuite.com/portal/resource/articles/business-strategy/inflation-effect-on-business.shtml>
- Nurjannah, , & Andiny. (2020). Characteristics Study of Street Vendors and Influence on Labor Absorption. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Economic and Social Science, ICON-ESS*. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.17-10-2018.2294103>
- Nyagudi (2022). War Crimes Avoidance & Detection: Battlefield Management Systems | Office of Justice Programs. (n.d.). Retrieve from: <https://www.ojp.gov/ncjrs/virtual-library/abstracts/war-crimes-avoidance-detection-battlefield-management-systems>
- Olayemi. (2023). *Building resilience and adaptability in the face of challenges*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/building-resilience-adaptability-face-challenges-samuel-olayemi?fbclid=IwAR0pXRB1JtEI4VO4CJGGEFwZg0SG4-rPGY8ix49SRotcWEWXuBaB5yilrH8>
- Ordinario, C. (2020, October 6). Ambulant vendors kept September prices low? Philippine Institute for Development Studies. Retrieved April 29, 2023, from <https://www.pids.gov.ph/details/ambulant-vendors-kept-september-prices-low>
- Philippine Statistical Authority [PSA]. (2023). Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved April 10, 2023, from <https://psa.gov.ph/price-indices/cpi-ir>
- Recchi, S. (2021). Informal street vending: a comparative literature review. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 41(7/8), 805–825. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijssp-07-2020-0285>
- Silver, M. (2006). Core inflation measures and statistical issues in choosing among them. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=902763>
- Solis, N. (2022). Inflation grips L.A. taco vendors: Less meat? Raise prices? Absorb losses? - Los Angeles Times. *Los Angeles Times*. <https://www.latimes.com/california/story/2022-07-02/taco-stands-feel-the-bite-of-inflation-as-meat-gas-prices-soar?fbclid=IwAR1pHAzbh43MYZecWvc6K0-xVoUyolxjfGv7y4ulPMTRuXlh1ukF8WqSzm0>
- Summary Inflation Report Consumer Price Index (2018=100): December 2022 | Philippine Statistics Authority. (n.d.). <https://psa.gov.ph/statistics/survey/price/summaryinflation-report-consumer-price-index-2018100-december-2022>
- Thompson., Jr. (2014). *Strategies for Staying Cost competitive*. Harvard Business Review. <https://hbr.org/1984/01/strategies-for-staying-cost-competitive?fbclid=IwAR0pXRB1JtEI4VO4CJGGEFwZg0SG4-rPGY8ix49SRotcWEWXuBaB5yilrH8>
- Thomson. (2023). *Skyrocketing inflation worsens student mental health crisis*. Open Access Government. <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/skyrocketing-inflation-worsens-student-mental-health-crisis/159213/?fbclid=IwAR0pXRB1JtEI4VO4CJGGEFwZg0SG4-rPGY8ix49SRotcWEWXuBaB5yilrH8>

- Webadmin. (2023). The importance of inventory management in your supply chain - Global Supply Chain Institute | Haslam College. *Global Supply Chain Institute | Haslam College of Business*. https://supplychainmanagement.utk.edu/blog/the-importance-of-inventory-management-in-your-supply-chain/?fbclid=IwAR1UWZUMjlfklju-2k97sgAR93-CBafBSH_tcEydjUfV_AIEgUdIX3OGvPU
- Weber, I. M. (n.d.). Sellers' Inflation, Profits and Conflict: Why can Large Firms Hike Prices in an Emergency? ScholarWorks@UMass Amherst. https://scholarworks.umass.edu/econ_workingpaper/343/
- Wichmann, J. R., Uppal, A., Sharma, A., & Dekimpe, M. G. (2022). A global perspective on the marketing mix across time and space. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 39(2), 502–521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2021.09.001>
- Williamson, O. E. (1979). Transaction-Cost Economics: The governance of Contractual relations. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 22(2), 233–261. <https://doi.org/10.1086/466942>
- Yin (1964). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. The Case Study Research: Design and Methods.
- Yin. (2014). *Case Study Research Design and Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. 282 pages. *The Canadian Journal of Program Evaluation*. <https://doi.org/10.3138/cjpe.30.1.108>
- Yu, L. S. (2022). Palengke vendors battle inflation: 'Kaya pa rin, kahit hindi n kaya'. Rappler. Retrieved March 22, 2023, from <https://www.rappler.com/business/philippine-market-vendors-battle-inflation/>
- Zhao, H., Yao, X., Liu, Z., & Qin, Y. (2021). Impact of pricing and product information on consumer buying behavior with customer satisfaction in a mediating role. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.720151>
- Zhu, J., & Simarmata, H. A. (2015). Formal land rights versus informal land rights: Governance for sustainable urbanization in the Jakarta metropolitan region, Indonesia. *Land Use Policy*, 43, 63–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2014.10.016>